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The electrosensory lateral line lobe (ELL) in mormyrid fish : a stepping stone to the understanding of the cerebellum ?
(Part 1/2 : the ELL)

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The electrosensory lateral line lobe (ELL) in mormyrid fish : a stepping stone to the understanding of the cerebellum ? (Part 1/2 : the ELL)

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Rob Beunis is a clinical neuropsychiatrist, (Antwerp, Belgium), retired, interested in the neurosciences.

Keywords : Decorrelation, adaptive filtering, memory addressing, electrosensory lateral line lobe, electric fish, unipolar brush cells, medium ganglion cells, broad spike, large fusiform cells, efferent cells, juxtalobar nucleus, cerebellum, bidirectional plasticity, granule cells, parallel fibers, Purkinje cells.

ABSTRACT

The electrosensory lateral line lobe (ELL) of electric fish is called ‘cerebellum-like’, suggesting that its study might offer clues as to how the cerebellum itself operates. Indeed, the ELL resembles (the cortex of) the cerebellum by displaying parallel fibers, granule cells and Purkinje-like cells in near identical relationships.

The fish ‘pollutes’ the electrosensory signals it receives by the electrosensory disturbances it inevitably generates itself by the use of its electric organ and its own muscles. The purpose of the ELL is to ‘clean’ these signals from this self-inflicted noise.

Research unveiled that the ELL implements a ‘decorrelation procedure’, since it extracts the signal component which is NOT correlated with the use of the electric organ or of muscles. It kind of partitions the signal in timeslices, and allocates memory to each timeslice to store a value that represents ‘the negative’ of the correlated signal value of the moment. The decorrelated signal emerges from the subtraction of the correlated component from the actual signal.

This article (Part 1 : the ELL) will be dedicated to an analysis of the decorrelation procedure which the ELL performs. For a start, decorrelation will be ‘captured’ in a simple ‘in silico’ computer demo program. With a few code lines the essence of decorrelation can be ‘visualized’. An array for memory and an averaging formula embedded in two nested loops are the ingredients.

Subsequently, adaptations will be inserted by following a reasoning line as to what implementation requirements are to be expected and respected in a neurocircuitry setting (in particular that of the ELL of mormyrid fish) and concepts will be defined that facilitate further reasoning.

The specialised research literature provides valuable information for this quest, and some simulation studies will be reviewed with these implementation requirements in mind.

The demo program generates a number of insights as to which strategies the ELL might deploy to prevent the corruption of its purpose, by displaying the effects without and with the use of a remedy.

There are indeed some problematic issues (formulated as ‘input load variability’ and ‘wrong addressing’), that several simulation studies apparently ignored or evaded. Memory addressing, plasticity rules, feedback systems, a signal annulling method : all will be important topics for discussion.

The literature citations often show that an idea is already ‘living’ in the field.

The question always lingering in mind will be if the cerebellum itself applies the ELL strategies. Everything that has added value for the understanding of the ELL itself, by the same token is also relevant for the cerebellum.

With this mixture of review, reasoning and speculation I just want to propose some ideas and to stir some brainstorming. Approach it with a critical mind when it concerns the reasoning, yet with an open mind when you think it deviates from so-called ‘established fact’.

The second article (Part 2 : the cerebellum) expands on the ‘identified problems’ and insights formulated in Part 1, focusing now on the cerebellum and its dissimilarities with the ELL.

At the end of it, a ‘basic algorithm’ hypothesis will be proposed – and it will appear that the essence of it was already formulated quite a while ago.

Part 1 consists of the following sections :

- A) Decorrelation 'in silico'
- B) Decorrelation 'in cerebello'
- C) Memory addressing 'in cerebello' – time-locked
- D) Memory addressing 'in cerebello' – state-locked
- E) Input load variability
- F) Wrong addressing - correlated
- G) Wrong addressing – uncorrelated
- H) Signal 'lifting' by non-associative potentiation
- I) Signal 'lifting' by added excitation
- J) The 'Traffic density fluctuation signal'

Each section builds on the former ones. They all end with a recapitulating conclusion.

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METHOD

Ample use is made of a program written in Visual Foxpro 9.0 . It 'visualizes' the decorrelation procedure under its different implementation variants and it is used to show the effects of corrupting factors and eventual remedies. The demos by no means claim to be 'simulations', but they serve the purpose to 'render' (and test) the underlying reasoning.

As pc programs they cannot really be run in this article, but screenshots ('stills') can be shown, and 'videolinks' are provided to mp4 files which are a 'recording' of the specific demo runs.

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A) DECORRELATION IN SILICO

Abbreviations used in this section :

CB-like	Cerebellum-like	ICTS	Iteration-correlated timeslice
CC	The correlated component	LTD/P	Long term depression/potentiation
CF	Climbing fiber	P	Potentiate / Potentiation
D	Depress / Depression	PF	Parallel fiber
DS	The signal to be decorrelated	PuC	Purkinje(like) cell
	aDS The actual DS	SS	Synapse strength
ELL	Electrosensory lateral line lobe	aSS	The actual SS
GrC	Granule cell	UC	The uncorrelated component

Please note that I will use the abbreviation 'PuC' to stand for PuCs proper and PuC-like cells as well.

Analogously, the expression 'in cerebello' is to be understood to include 'in cerebello-like'.

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

CB-like structures based on PuCs, PFs and GrCs perform signal decorrelation to implement adaptive filtering e.g. in the ELL of mormyrid fish.

[1] (Sawtell et al. 2008)

"Sensory information is often acquired through active exploration.

However, an animal's own movements may result in changes in patterns of sensory input that could interfere with the detection and processing of behaviorally relevant sensory signals.

Neural mechanisms for predicting the sensory consequences of movements are thus likely to be of general importance for sensory systems. Such mechanisms have been identified in cerebellum-like structures associated with electrosensory processing in fish.

These structures are hypothesized to act as adaptive filters, removing correlations between incoming sensory input and central predictive signals through associative plasticity at parallel fiber synapses."

A first demo starts with a 'visualization' of a signal decorrelation procedure based on an averaging formula. See Fig. 1 (showing the end result of a run) but also use the videolink to get acquainted with the demo program.

In each of the 5 histograms a 'signal' is represented by a 250-element array, with each array element standing for a 'timeslice' and holding the 'value' of the signal at each particular timeslice moment.

A signal S3 is 'fed' 250 times to a decorrelation procedure, with S3 at each iteration being the sum of an unchanging S1 (generated once at the start) and an everchanging S2 (generated anew before each iteration with a random function).

The whole setup implies that S1 and S2 are time-correlated with reference to the start of each iteration.

The procedure is expected to generate the signals S4 and S5, where S4 will 'emerge' from S3 as the correlated component [CC], and where S5 will be computed by subtracting S4 from S3, yielding the uncorrelated component [UC].

To visualize the growing 'match', the modulation of S4 is projected over S1, and vice-versa, same for S5 and S2.

To quantify the remaining mismatch, a 'fit'-histogram, based on a sum of squares of differences formula, shows the progress of the convergence of S5 towards S2.

In this actual demo the 'core' decorrelation formula is a plain averaging algorithm : it involves using an extra array to keep track of the growing sums for each of the 250 timeslices, necessary to calculate the 250 averages by dividing the sums by the iteration counter.

See how the fit (smaller is better) evolves with increasing iterations.

A small error remains (and will remain) but nevertheless the decorrelation (and hence the application as an 'adaptive filter') is strikingly performant.

Fig. 1 Videolink : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/r8prd9olxafm8mq/demo-1-5.mp4?dl=0>

Averaging the 'iteration-correlated timeslices' [ICTSs] of an unchanging signal (S1) yields the original signal, but averaging the ICTSs of a purely randomly changing signal (S2) evolves towards a flat signal since in that case the averages of all the ICTSs statistically converge.

Hence S4 becomes S1 (i.e. shows the same modulation) but S4 is 'lifted' by the addition of the S2-ICTSs-average.

Subtracting S4 from S3 produces S5, the modulation of which should reflect the uncorrelated modulation of S2, but here a constant is added to keep it in the positive range for the sake of the display.

Same where needed to fit the projected modulation 'skylines' vertically together.

The modulations of S1 and S2 (and hence those of S3 and S4 too) were deliberately kept in the positive range, but later cases will be considered where the input is inverted.

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It is a surprisingly simple method to decorrelate a signal, but let's adapt it for implementation by a neurocircuit.

The use of an 'extra array of sums' better be avoided, and the next average value directly derived out of the former one at every iteration.

The series of average values while iterating taking the form

$v1 / 1$, $(v1 + v2) / 2$, $(v1 + v2 + v3) / 3$ etc. ,

and since e.g. $(v1 + v2 + v3) / 3 = [(v1 + v2) * 1 / 2 + v3 / 2] * 2 / 3$

the formula can be rewritten as follows (with AVG = average and ic = the iteration counter) :

Next AVG = (Actual AVG + Actual S3 value / ic) * [ic / (ic + 1)]

and its form can be further modified to become :

Next AVG = Actual AVG - Actual AVG * x% + Actual S3 value * x% , with $x\% = 1 / (ic + 1)$.

Inserting this new formula in the demo program produces the same result.

<https://www.dropbox.com/s/cbvqci552ap7k8i/demo-1-6.mp4?dl=0>

...

Since this formula will resurface regularly, let's rewrite it with the abbreviations also used later on :

Next SS = aSS - aSS * x% + aDS * x%

In this formula :

SS stands for 'synapse strength' (synapses will be considered to be used as engrams representing the average values),

DS stands for 'the signal to be decorrelated' (S3 in the demo)

while the prefix 'a' refers to 'the actual value of '.

The 'a' takes the place of indexes like (ts,i) since this formula is to be seen as 'enveloped' by an inner loop covering the 'timeslices' (ts) of the DS, and an outer loop representing the number of iterations (i) through the inner loop.

Several simulation studies exhibit the same 'nested loop' structure e.g. :

[2] (Roberts and Bell, 2000)

"The representation of time will be broken into cycles parametrized by two variables, (x; t), where x denotes the time following each electric organ command, and t represents the number of EOD cycles." (EOD = Electric organ discharge)

With long term potentiation [LTP] and depression [LTD] in mind - we can rephrase this formula as :

"Depress [D] the synapse with a % of its actual strength and then potentiate [P] it with the same % but now proportionate to the actual signal value".

...

We have to consider however that an x% value depending on an iteration counter is highly improbable in vivo, so let's get rid of it and fill in a fixed % of our own choice (which here is still a same % for D and P : $p = d = x$).

Fig. 2 shows the 'fit'-histograms for values for x of 1%, 2%, 5% and 10%.

Apparently, higher percentages perform better in speed but end up with less matching precision.

The initial averaging formula sweeps the value of x over a whole range as a function of the iteration counter ic, starting with a large % and progressively using a smaller one.

(Activate <https://www.dropbox.com/s/cbvqci552ap7k8i/demo-1-6.mp4?dl=0> again and observe the P and D values.)

In doing so it succeeds in having both speedy improvement and good matching precision. Mathematically it is the best strategy, but in vivo an incremental / decremental approach using small steps is more plausible and it is also nearly as good, since matching precision is reached after an acceptable number of iterations.

Fig. 2

- x=1% : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/pynnsv1evy2pihw/demo-1-7.mp4?dl=0>
- x=2% : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/yp9xx5ahb0mcqge/demo-1-8.mp4?dl=0>
- x=5% : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/8a0r7m80j2x2u27/demo-1-9.mp4?dl=0>
- x=10% : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/63q37cwnl1a2p3k/demo-1-10.mp4?dl=0>

...

Let's now observe what happens when using different %'s for D (d%) and P (p%) (see Fig. 3) :

Fig. 3

- p=2% d=3% <https://www.dropbox.com/s/fl7m9dkxejbj7zz/demo-1-14.mp4?dl=0>
- p=3% d=2% <https://www.dropbox.com/s/0htmc1dvbxnyvd6/demo-1-13.mp4?dl=0>
- p=2% d=5% <https://www.dropbox.com/s/9pdkfaffyzq0fxj/demo-1-12.mp4?dl=0>
- p=5% d=2% <https://www.dropbox.com/s/jj8fhnw3qi4wjpt/demo-1-11.mp4?dl=0>

The more p and d differ the more the result deteriorates and very quickly the situation becomes totally unstable !

Note : when the fit histogram rises out of bounds (like it does for p=5% d=2%) its height is reduced with an appropriate factor (cfr the box message in the video) and when the 'modulatory range' of S4 or S5 goes out of sight (in the video again), a portion of the added UC-average (indicated by the appearance of a white bar) is left out.

Finally let's observe what jitter does to the result in the following videos :

- p=d=2%, jitter added to S2 : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/pjdjp0z xu2m7ddp/demo-1-15.mp4?dl=0>

It is the essence of the decorrelation procedure to separate the correlated from the uncorrelated, be it jitter or something else.

- p=d=2%, jitter added to S1 : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/fqm0o1kfbvhgqge/demo-1-16.mp4?dl=0>

Adding jitter to S1 boils down to the same : it is decorrelated as being part of the uncorrelated component.

However, although the matching is 'visually' still very good, the 'fit'-histogram seems to indicate otherwise, but it is affected by the high frequency changes which randomly enlarge the differences between consecutive timeslices in S5, on which the fit calculation relies.

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This 'playing with the parameters' makes it clear that - *in this particular 'in silico' setup* - D and P have to be 'balanced' and 'coupled' i.e. both D and P adjustments have to be executed immediately one after the other, if not simultaneously.

When not finely 'balanced', decorrelation quality rapidly deteriorates, and when not 'coupled' the necessary 'calculation base values' (aSS and aDS resp.) get lost (since replaced by new actual values).

With D and P relying on different biological implementation mechanisms, this balancing would imply a fine adjustment of the mechanisms relative to each other to assure "a matching of %'s".

In principle these mechanisms might be locally in place at the synapse level, having been adjusted by evolution, discarding the need for some kind of external 'teaching signal'.

It doesn't exclude the possibility that a 'teaching signal' is used to guide the adjustment, but the demo program also shows - *in this case of signal decorrelation setup* - that a 'teaching signal' (from a climbing fiber or any other signal brought in from outside) is no necessity : just feed the signal proper repetitively into the decorrelator and it does the job.

Let's, for now, just refer to an interesting article by Tzounopoulos (2007) wherein he reports the finding that two opposite adjustments of plasticity are being activated at the same time.

[3] (Tzounopolis et al. 2007)

"Recent reports suggest that synaptic plasticity results from the balance between separately activated induction pathways for LTP and LTD (Bender et al., 2006; Liu et al., 2004; O'Connor et al., 2005; Wang et al., 2005; Wittenberg and Wang, 2006) ."

"Our results differ in that we find that LTP and LTD mechanisms have different sites of action (pre- versus postsynaptic) yet occur simultaneously."

In these cases, linear summation of LTP and LTD components determine the overall associative plasticity rule outcome.

Such a mechanism might allow a synapse to 'settle' and 'hover' around a value (e.g. the average) with little 'ups and downs' in a continuous adjusting process.

It is bidirectional plasticity, but with the extra requirement that it be (quasi)-simultaneous.

[3] (Tzounopolis et al. 2007)

"Most strikingly, we find that these distinct signaling pathways occur simultaneously and thus together determine the sign of the observed plasticity and shape the timing window."

The Tzounopolos article however focuses on the Dorsal Cochlear Nucleus, in particular on cartwheel cells, and it is not clear if these interesting cells perform a decorrelation operation.

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CONCLUSION

To get acquainted with a decorrelation process, an 'in silico' implementation was written : a demo program.

Some neurobiological issues were already considered (avoiding the storage of intermediate results, preferring an 'adjustment by small steps' approach) and the PF-PuC synapses are to take the cardinal memory role (like the 250-element-array does) with local plasticity mechanisms at these synapses implementing an averaging computation.

Using this specific decorrelation algorithm, it appears that 'balanced and coupled' small adjustment steps are necessary conditions to achieve quality decorrelation, suggesting that these might also be mandatory 'in cerebello' concerning LTD and LTP plasticity 'ruling' at the PF-PuC synapse site.

For the specific issue of signal decorrelation, the whole demo questions the presumed role as 'a teacher' for the CF (although - of course - there must be some good reason for its presence).

Finally, a Tzounopolis article gives a hint that a 'coupled balance' type of plasticity might exist.

Let's now push the transposition from 'in silico' to 'in cerebello' still further.

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B) DECORRELATION IN CEREBELLO

Abbreviations used in this section :

A-path	Activation path	GrC	Granule cell
AS	Activating signal	GrL	Granular layer (or EGp in CB-like structures)
CB-like	Cerebellum-like	MF	Mossy fiber
DS	The signal to be decorrelated	PF	Parallel fiber
EGp	Eminentia granularis posterior	PuC	Purkinje(like) cell
GS	Guiding signal		

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

PF-PuC synapses will be held to take the 'memory role' of the demo-array, each synapse devoted to holding a timeslice-related value of the DS, values destined by local plasticity mechanisms to converge towards timeslice-averages at every iteration over the same series of synapses.

Addressing specific PF-PuC-synapses must be effected through GrCs, the origins of the PFs, and it would mean activating shortly (a timeslice) one GrC after another, in a chain.

I will refer to such a chain of sequentially activated synapses (or PFs or GrCs) as an 'activation path' [A-path] ('path' is a mental picture : the actual involved GrCs/PFs/synapses are spatially scattered).

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Note : I describe the 'A-path' here as a 'one-dimensional chain' of sequentially activated single GrCs and PF-PuC synapses, but of course, in vivo, whole populations of GrCs and PF-PuC synapses are activated in parallel, and then an A-path becomes a 'chain of synapse populations' (with activation times clustered around a specific timeslice). Since these populations can be expected to differ in size, it brings in additional parameters that have to be taken into account at some point.

You will regularly recognize this 'one-dimensional' style of description in the text : it is often simpler to develop an argumentation this way. You will realize that the demos and many simulations in the field are also 'one-dimensional' in this sense. When, however, population size matters, it will be explicitly noted.

This said, let's focus on the requirements an A-path should comply with.

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The absolute location of the synapses pertaining to an A-path is of no importance (as is the absolute address of memory locations in silico), but they must stay allocated to 'their' specific path, to be addressed again if necessary.

In other words : the particular A-path taken in the synapse landscape is of no importance - it may be any sequence - but it is mandatory that somehow the exact same path can be reconstructed when circumstances call for it :

- 1) The A-path must be reproducible (Mauk and Donegan - although in a context of conditioning and applying it to the conditioned stimulus - stress it) :

[4] (Mauk and Donegan, 1997)

“Conditioning requires a degree of across-trials consistency in the CS representation because a CS can only elicit CRs if it activates, within a narrow window of time, a sufficient number of the synapses that were modified by previous CS + US pairings.

Given our assumption that the CS is represented as a sequence of granule cell subsets active at different times during the stimulus, it is necessary that the ordering of this sequence be consistent from one trial to the next.

Specifically, the time-varying pattern of granule cell activity must be consistent from one trial to the next over the range of ISIs effective in producing conditioning.

Consequently, decreases in across-trials consistency of granule activity should degrade the rate of conditioning, and variations in across-trials consistency for different segments of the CS would result in different rates of learning for different ISIs.”

Moreover - obvious but not trivial - each synapse is to represent one and only one particular 'step' in the A-path, if it were used twice or more to represent other steps, 'averages' would become compounded and hence useless (a problem tackled later) :

- 2) The A-path (and each step in it) must be unique.

Finally, the A-path needs to have a temporal resolution fine enough to allow (downstream) the construction of an equally fine-tuned signal that can serve to correct a DS : if resolution falls short decorrelation quality will suffer :

3) The A-path must have adequate temporal resolution.

Every proposal for implementation of an A-path must check if it satisfies these criteria and whenever the 'A-path' concept is invoked it will be implied that it does.

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Can the kind of signalling traffic that is measured in countless research experiments be reconciled with the concept of such an A-path (and its requirements) ?

I simply see no other way (in ELL and cerebellum) to address and adjust iteratively and correctly a memory bank that is needed to implement decorrelation.

Hence, I believe that it is indeed one of the main purposes of the granular layer [GrL] (which - in CB-like structures - will refer to the eminentia granularis posterior [EGp]) to allocate a set of synapses in the PuC to hold values related to timeslices of the DS. So, headstrong, I will proceed with the concept of the A-path. In any case, by and large, this concept is already embraced by the researchers in the field of the ELL, as we will see.

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In programming, the 'higher language' transparently (meaning invisibly) takes care of the managing, allocating and addressing of memory.

In the demo the A-path simply was defined and laid out as an array (of memory locations) which is addressed via programming commands, and program execution being serial (in standard pcs), sequential addressing and timeslicing is an automatic consequence.

In silico it is evident that the DS has no role in the managing and addressing of memory, it provides content for it.

In cerebello I see the creation of an A-path as the result of a different kind of neural signalling, fed into the GrL via the mossy fibers [MFs] or/and produced by a dedicated neurocircuit located in it.

Again, for the sake of expression brevity - I call those 'signals that guide the activation process' collectively the 'G' signals or GSs.

By definition the GSs refer to signalling upstream of the GrCs, and when the processing of the GSs at the GrC results in firing it, I refer to this 'downstream' signal - which is going to affect synapses at the PuC - as the 'activating signal' [AS].

The GSs are the cerebellar counterpart of the programming commands in silico - with the DS taking no role in it - so I want the GSs to be clearly distinguished from the DS !

In the research literature focused on the cerebellum I found no explicit mention of such 'dichotomy' of signal functionality, although the observation that input to GrCs can be unimodal or multimodal might hint at it

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CONCLUSION

With PuCs acting as a 'memory bank', GrCs are assumed to address specific locations in it at specific times, and when 'imagining' that these spatial locations are strung together in the temporal order of their addressing, we get the spatiotemporal 'picture' of an A-path.

Requirements for the A-path to be functional are listed : reproducibility, uniqueness and adequate temporal resolution.

It is proposed that the A-path is constructed by way of 'guiding signals' (GSs) which are going to determine which GrCs are to fire at which moment.

GSs stand in stark contrast with the DS, the modulation of which carries information that is to be processed to construct a corrective signal that has a meaningful relation to it, and therefore I insist on clearly distinguishing between the DS and the GSs.

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C) MEMORY ADDRESSING IN CEREBELLO – TIME-LOCKED

Abbreviations used in this section :

A-path	Activation path	ESD	Electrosensory disturbance
AS	Activating signal	GS	Guiding signal
CB-like	Cerebellum-like	GoC	Golgi cell
CC	The correlated component	GrC	Granule cell
CS	Conditioned stimulus	GrL	Granular layer (or EGp in CB-like structures)
DS	The signal to be decorrelated	MF	Mossy fiber
EGp	Eminentia granularis posterior	MGC	Medium ganglion cell
ELL	Electrosensory lateral line lobe	PF	Parallel fiber
EO	Electric organ	PuC	Purkinje(like) cell
EOCD	Electric organ corollary discharge	UBC	Unipolar brush cell
EOD	Electric organ discharge		

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

In the ELL however, the distinction between DS and GSs is made by anatomy.

Let's return to our 'primitive' mormyrid fish with their electric organ [EO] discharges [EODs].

[5] (Kennedy et al. 2014)

“Weakly electric mormyrid fish emit brief EOD pulses for communication and active electrolocation. However, the fish’s own EOD also affects passive electroreceptors tuned to detect external fields.”

“Previous studies have shown that such interference, a ringing pattern of activation that may persist for as long as the interval between EODs, is cancelled out in medium ganglion cells through the generation of motor corollary discharge responses that are temporally-specific negative images of the sensory consequences of the EOD .”

Fig. 4 from [5] (Kennedy et al. 2014)

In the ELL, and considering medium ganglion cells [MGCs], the DS (input from electroreceptors) is routed to the basal dendrites, while the GSs come in by MFs, and will activate GrCs (in the EGp) which impact on the MGCs by way of the PFs (Fig. 4).

I intentionally start with the publication of Kennedy-Wayne-Sawtell (2014) because it focuses purely on the problem of how the fish is able to generate a 'negative image' (necessary to cancel the sensory consequences of the EOD), by using paralyzed fish. This way, the EOD is blocked (not the EO corollary discharge [EOCD]) and there are also no movements to confound the issue.

The EOCD normally signals the coming of the self-induced electro-sensory disturbance [ESD], but in itself it is too short to cover the timespan it takes for the disturbance to die out.

[5] (Kennedy et al. 2014)

“Most mossy fibers recorded in EGp exhibited responses restricted to short delays, termed early and medium, that closely resembled the responses recorded in midbrain neurons that send mossy fibers to EGp. Thus corollary discharge inputs to EGp appear insufficient for cancelling the effects of the EOD over their entire duration.”

In this special case we can look at the EOCD as an example of a GS that lacks 'resolution power'.

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Kennedy et al. however observed a cascade of MF-activity following the EOCD, the EOCD apparently entraining a set of unipolar brush cells [UBCs] with different reaction types.

[5] (Kennedy et al. 2014)

“However, we also found other putative mossy fibers within EGp, termed late and pause, that exhibited far more delayed and diverse corollary discharge responses. Late mossy fibers fire bursts or single action potentials at long delays after the EOD command (>50 ms), while pause mossy fibers show highly regular tonic firing that ceases abruptly around the time of the command.”

“A candidate for the source of late and pause responses recorded in EGp are the UBCs that, in mormyrid fish as in the mammalian cerebellum and dorsal cochlear nucleus, give rise to an intrinsic system of mossy fiber axons that provides additional excitatory input to granule cells.”

UBCs receive input from one MF, show diverse and prolonged reactions upon stimulation and channel their output via 'intrinsic mossy fibers' which - like the extrinsic ones - at their turn contact GrCs.

They contact also other UBCs, allowing for still more prolonged cascading.

[6] (Gao et al. 2012)

“Part of the diversity spreading is embedded in the hardware connections rather than mediated by plasticity. UBCs may form an essential link in this respect. The extent of diversity spreading and the processing time window will be more prominent when the circuitry is enriched by the feedforward excitation exerted by UBCs, which are inserted into the granule cell network in a serial fashion, either as single or as multiple, consecutively ordered elements.”

Even without plasticity, these superimposed elements in the network allow the granular layer to induce delays in changes of firing rate for periods of hundreds of milliseconds and to generate prolonged periods of increased firing that can vary from hundreds to even thousands of milliseconds.”

The net effect is that an A-path can be constructed that covers the whole timespan of the DS, and that timing diversity is 'injected', improving the resolution.

[5] (Kennedy et al. 2014)

“Model granule cell populations lacking late and pause inputs provide a far less effective basis for cancellation, indicating an important role for the temporally diverse and delayed corollary discharge responses generated by UBCs.”

In this (relatively) primitive setting, with a structure dedicated to correcting a single 'modality' (electroreception), the GS sent in 'from above' is hardly more than a timing signal, but then - locally in the granular mass - it is empowered by the UBCs.

...

The EOCD detailed signal structure seems to be of no importance, it just has to trigger the UBCs, which then produce signals that can have no added informative value either.

This is not to say that the UBC-signal structure doesn't matter, but it gives more weight to the view that it are only the physical particularities of the GSs that count - not their encoded 'meaning' - and it are these particularities that ultimately lead to 'choosing a set of synapses' in the PuC, by activating in sequence a series of GrCs.

We should therefore not be surprised that 'the message is lost' in all the converging, distorting and mixing up of the GrC-inputs (certainly in multimodal circumstances).

Understanding this is very important, since many seem to think that somehow the PuCs must be able to extract 'sense' out of the GSs, even after them being so 'messed up' in the GrL.

The DS however, must preserve its meaning relative to its source, and the signal should reach the PuC unspoiled, since the output after decorrelation must also be 'meaningful' relative to it (e.g. when it is to be a negative image to cancel the CC in the DS).

...

Fig. 5 from [7] (Mugnaini et al. 2010)

UBCs produce a temporally expanded, time-diversified signal and prolong it even more when they are serially connected (Fig. 5).

UBCs also partake in spreading the signal spatially, and when serially connected they multiply this spread.

[8] (Van Dorp et al. 2015)

“The strategic position in the granular layer circuitry allows a single UBC to directly affect hundreds of granule cells.”

'Cascades' can be formed with a 'diverging-only' structure, since there are no excitatory 'horizontal' connections between different cascades.

Dendrites of GrCs can 'plug in' at every level of such a cascade, a 'top one' receiving the MF signal proper without delay, GrCs sampling at lower and lower levels receiving signal modulations with increasing delays.

One reason for this spatial spreading may be that the amount of MFs bringing in the (simple and stereotyped) EOCD is vastly smaller than the amount of memory units (PF-PuC synapses addressed by GrCs) which are going to be needed to 'construct' a negative image of due resolution.

...

Can UBCs guarantee that the requirement of 'uniqueness' is satisfied ?

Uniqueness being the condition that each step in an A-path is represented by a different GrC (implying also that it may only fire during its allocated timeslice), we need a lot of GrCs that fire in sequence.

'Spatial spreading' is of no avail if it results in having a lot of GrCs firing in unison.

I presume however that different UBC-cascades not necessarily are triggered or react simultaneously, and that it is also possible that 'AND-gating' different combinations of UBC-outputs at the GrC can break up the unison and can cause a whole population of GrCs receiving inputs from different UBC-cascades to fire at different moments (I dwell some more on the subject in the related 'Addendum' at the end of this article).

If UBCs were 'digital' I would immediately see them as ideal 'enrichers' of time-structure, reproducing exactly the same cascade of events at every iteration, but being biological, it remains to be demonstrated that their internal signalling cascades are so time-locked and invariant relative to the trigger input that even cascaded and as a population they can each time reproduce the same output.

It would be great if it could be shown that an EOCD always triggers the same cascaded responses in small groups of cascaded UBCs since without reproducibility the system makes no sense.

[5] (Kennedy et al. 2014)

“Corollary discharge responses were observed in 170 of 184 granule cells and consisted of prominent depolarizations with temporal patterns that are highly consistent across commands.”

Evince a pattern that is concealed in the consecutive activating of hundreds of GrCs seems hopelessly difficult however.

[9] (Chen et al. 2017)

“Measures of population sparseness will ultimately require simultaneous monitoring of many GrCs during whisker movement (or monitoring of PF activity) to examine the fraction and identification of active GrCs in Crus I.”

...

UBCs appear also in the vestibular and in the auditory system and we might wonder why their use is needed there.

These systems work with rotational parameters and I imagine that small or slow changes in coordinates may be correlated with large or speedy (and eventually complicated) movements (like with near gimbal lock situations in mechanics), requiring an A-path with a finer resolution than the modulation in the GSs alone is able to generate.

[10] (Zampini et al. 2017)

“Granular layer network modeling indicates that phase dispersion of UBC responses generates diverse phase coding in the granule cell population, allowing climbing-fiber-driven Purkinje cell learning at arbitrary phases of the vestibular input.”

“According to a computer model, this variability in UBC responses ensures that a subset of UBCs will always be active at any point during vestibular input. This in turn means that Purkinje cells can fire at any stage of a movement, which boosts the learning of motor skills.”

“Our data support a preferential role of UBCs in tasks in which non trivial associations between inputs and outputs at different phases need to be learned, like phase-shifted VOR or high-velocity compensatory eye movements during which non-linear inverse eye dynamics have to be computed (Green et al., 2007; Lisberger, 2009).”

This may be an explanation for the prominent presence of UBCs there, which in these cases are engaged by head movement, vestibular or auditory (and not necessarily time-fixed) inputs.

It begs the question if UBCs can be 'modulated' to follow a signal development that is not time-fixed but time-correlated with another reference signal in which time (the speed) might be a variable.

[11] (Subramaniam et al. 2014)

“Through the late onset response (LOR), UBCs can translate the intensity of the input (coded as the number of active fibers and duration of their discharge) into output bursts with different delay, duration and frequency. This implements a time-code that could reverberate through the network along the chains made by UBCs with other UBCs and granule cells (Nunzi and Mugnaini, 2000; Nunzi et al., 2001).”

[12] (Van Dorp et al. 2014)

“We show that a granular layer interneuron, called the unipolar brush cell, is well suited to represent time intervals in a robust way in the cerebellar cortex. Unipolar brush cells exhibited delayed increases in excitatory synaptic input in response to presynaptic stimulation in mouse cerebellar slices. Depending on the frequency of stimulation, delays extended from zero up to hundreds of milliseconds. Such controllable protraction of delayed currents was the result of an unusual mode of synaptic integration, which was well described by a model of steady-state AMPA receptor activation.”

“A direct result of the integrative properties of the synapse was the ability for individual UBCs to controllably extend slow synaptic transmission delays. Such functionality is of particular relevance in the context of cerebellar timing and adaptation.”

“Comparing different UBCs, the extent of the delay varied widely between cells, which by itself could have important functional implications. For individual UBCs, modulation of the slow EPSC delay took place with little variation in EPSC amplitude, allowing for a fully independent representation of temporal intervals. Slow EPSCs were generated reliably on a trial-to-trial basis, and UBCs could accurately represent timing of slow signals in their action potential output.”

For still other questions cfr :

[7] (Mugnaini et al. 2010)

“Does the innervation from a specific source, e.g. vestibular nerve, vestibular nuclei and spinal cord, end upon specific UBC subclasses ?

Do the synaptic targets of PLCbeta4+ UBCs differ from those of CR+ or mGluR1alpha+ UBCs ?

Do the axons of all CR+ or mGluR1alpha+ UBCs innervate other UBCs belonging to the same subclass, as suggested by Nunzi et al. (2002) ?

May the type of mossy fiber input modulate expression of cell subclass-specific proteins in UBCs ?”

Elsewhere the GSs provided by the concerned modalities seem able to do with less or no support of UBCs to generate quality A-paths.

Probably it can be generalized that whenever the output signal needs more resolution (for timeslicing which requires a memory engram per timeslice) than the GS-input from upstream centers can provide, UBCs are intercalated.

...

The case of a GS consisting of a short 'announcing' EOD of which the temporal structure needs to be enriched by an UBC-neurocircuit internal to the granular layer demonstrates :

- that a GS is used for its physical time-structure only, since the UBC-added modulation cannot refer to any 'meaning' (as a proprioceptive or auditory or visual input would do).

- that although 'primitive' we see here a 'specialization' evolved to solve a problem of poor GS-structure.

- that 'the system' couldn't find any other internal 'reference'-signal having a time-structure that correlates with the EOD-caused ESD : indeed, when the EOD is 'launched' the ESD has a time-fixed development of its own and UBCs create GSs that do the same.

...

CONCLUSION

Examining a 'simple' case of decorrelation in mormyrid fish shows the use of a GS which has to be 'empowered' by UBCs to become functional as a constructor of an A-path.

In fact, UBC cascades are generating a spatiotemporal spread of GrC activation by being randomly diverse, thereby stressing the point that 'meaningful signal content' doesn't matter here.

Despite this 'randomness', the system with UBCs must be able to guarantee that the A-path satisfies its mandatory requirements, and that remains speculative and should be demonstrated.

The case discussed is a special example : we have the time-fixedness of the ESD (DS), and we have GSs which - in the absence of time-correlated reference signals in the system - are being assembled 'by artificial means' : using UBCs.

Finally, it is speculated that the presence of UBCs in systems with rotational parameters might be explained by the need - there too - to solve inherent resolution problems.

Let's now shift focus to systems that can rely on internal reference signals.

...

D) MEMORY ADDRESSING IN CEREBELLO – STATE-LOCKED

Abbreviations used in this section :

A-path	Activation path	ESD	Electrosensory disturbance
D	Depress / Depression	GS	Guiding signal
DS	The signal to be decorrelated	GrC	Granule cell
ELL	Electrosensory lateral line lobe	ISU	Input space unit
EO	Electric organ	MCCD	Motor command corollary discharge
EOCD	Electric organ corollary discharge	MF	Mossy fiber
EOD	Electric organ discharge	MGC	Medium ganglion cell
		UBC	Unipolar brush cell

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

A study by Bodznick, Montgomery and Carey (1999) concerns the passive electrosensory system in elasmobranch skates in which the electrosensory disturbances [ESDs] caused by ventilatory (and other) movements have to be cancelled out.

[13] (Bodznick et al. (1999)

“The ampullae of Lorenzini of sharks, skates and rays are the most sensitive electroreceptors known, and this is in keeping with their function as detectors of the very weak natural electric fields that exist in the sea (Murray, 1962; Kalmijn, 1971, 1974) . But extremely sensitive receptors are of no use without equally well-developed mechanisms for separating the important weak signals from the meaningless background noise that is often much stronger than the signals themselves.”

“A very common source of noise in sensory systems is self-stimulation created by an animal’s own behavior. For the elasmobranch electrosense, ventilatory movements cause potent self-stimulation; the fish literally cannot breathe without creating electrosensory inputs that can mask relevant external fields.”

“However, work on the skate electrosense over the last 10 years has demonstrated that selectively eliminating such self-generated noise and other predictable patterns of sensory inflow is a principal function of the very first electrosensory nucleus in the brain.”

In the mormyrids the ESD is provoked by a gunshotlike EOD but in the skates the ESD is electric 'noise' when (muscle) movements are made.

The parallelism between the state of the respiration muscles and the ESD makes the ESD time- and state-correlated with the movements and this can be exploited without need for an 'announcing signal' or even a notion of 'signal beginning' : the 'state' parameters in principle can be used as pointers to a location on the A-path and the 'unrolling' of the A-path follows faithfully the continuously evolving state.

The important consequence of this is that the A-path is at all times reproducible.

Usually several correlated signals (called reference signals) are available of which motor command corollary discharge [MCCD] and proprioceptive feedback are the prime candidates (amongst others) to be used as GSs for the construction of an A-path that automatically covers the necessary timespan.

[13] (Bodznick et al. 1999)

“Electrophysiological studies of the dorsal granular ridge (DGR) indicate that the parallel fibers carry central copies of motor commands, including ventilatory commands (Hjelmstad et al., 1996), proprioceptive signals related to movements and descending electrosensory feedback (New and Bodznick, 1990; Conley and Bodznick, 1994) .”

These signals logically are also intercorrelated, and hence using one or another of them suffices (if enough resolution power), but using them together is better and makes cancellation more robust.

[14] (Requarth et al. 2014)

“Internally generated motor corollary discharge signals and proprioceptive feedback represent separate sources of information either of which could, in principle, be used to distinguish between external versus self-generated sensory input.”

[15] (Bell et al. 1997A)

“The pairing with separate components among the set of signals present during normal respiration was clearly less effective in these fish than pairing with normal respiration itself. The methods chosen to test the individual components may not have been adequate, but it is also possible that the strongest effects in these fish are obtained only when all the available predictive signals occur together.”

When multiple intercorrelated reference signals are available one can even distinguish 'parallel A-paths', which all serve the purpose of decorrelating the same DS.

[13] (Bodznick et al. (1999)

“In the model of Montgomery and Bodznick (1994), the parallel fiber projection represents a rich matrix of reference signals (sensory and motor corollary discharge) with a wide range of specific temporal relationships to the fish’s behaviors. To construct the cancellation signal, the AEN need only select from this matrix the appropriate subset of reference signals whose activity is reliably correlated, positively or negatively, with the reafference.”

Requarth et al. explicitly investigate such a situation and pose the question how all these A-paths - working in isolation or together - are able to generate a more or less identical negative image.

[14] (Requarth et all. 2014)

“Before neuromuscular paralysis, microstimulation of the optic tectum is used to evoke a rapid tail movement that moves the electric organ closer to the receptive field of the recorded cell. After paralysis, microstimulation evokes movement motor commands in the absence of movement, allowing us to monitor the effect of CD signals on neural responses in the absence of proprioceptive feedback. In addition, we can move the tail passively with a computer-controlled stage in a way that mimics the tail movement evoked by tectal microstimulation before paralysis. This setup allows us to engage CD and proprioceptive inputs either separately or together and, as described next, to control their relationship to an ES .”

“A central finding of this study is that approximately equivalent negative images are formed using either CD or proprioception and that, under conditions approximating self-generated movements, both are used.”

...

Going back to the mormyrids there is an article in which Requarth and Sawtell (2014) now focus on the role of proprioception when mormyrids waggle their EO-bearing tail.

[16] (Requarth et al. 2014)

“Though previous studies of cerebellum-like structures have provided evidence for predictions based on corollary discharge signals, these accounts have been limited to simple, highly stereotyped behavior : i.e., ventilation in elasmobranch fish (Bodznick et al., 1999) and the EOD in weakly electric mormyrid fish (Bell, 1981) . Whereas the EOD motor command is simple and completely stereotyped, movement motor commands are obviously more complex and diverse.”

“Real movements activate proprioception, which provides an additional source of information that might be sufficient to cancel self-generated electrosensory input in the absence of corollary discharge (Bastian, 1995; Bastian et al., 2004; Bell et al., 1992; Sawtell, 2010; Sawtell and Williams, 2008) . Our results show that both corollary discharge and proprioceptive signals are used under conditions that simulate real movements.”

The tail (EO) movement has a non-synchronized effect on the ESD following the EOD and hence specific cancellation profiles are needed for all possible tail-position / ESD-timeslice pairs.

[16] (Requarth et al. 2014)

"Changes in the electric field due to movements of the electric organ in the tail are typically proportional to tail displacement from the midline, with tail movements toward the side of the receptive field resulting in an increase in the local electric field amplitude and an increase in electroreceptor activation."

“Simultaneously recorded motor commands to discharge the electric organ were entirely distinct from activity recorded from spinal motor nerves in that the timing of their occurrences was unrelated to motor nerve activity. Hence, motor nerve activity reflects commands related to swimming movements.”

The GSs here consist of two independent variables : on the one hand the EOCD+UBC signal, on the other hand the proprioceptive signal.

To produce a 'negative image' for each situation a whole family of A-paths is needed.

What was one-dimensional now becomes two-dimensional, and the A-path becomes an A-plane, meaning that it is the set of all possible A-paths that can be taken.

Sawtell (2010) is aware of this, reflecting about the need to combine EOCD and proprioception to create kind of a 2D-space in this situation, indicating even that it is in principle undesirable NOT to combine them.

[17] (Sawtell 2010)

“In short, PF inputs that represent either body position or motor command timing (proprioceptive and EOCD PFs) will lead to plastic changes at a specific position but at all times or at a specific time but at all positions. Clearly, a simple addition of such changes will not lead to plastic changes restricted to both position and time. Restricting plastic changes to certain positions and times requires PF inputs with activity confined to certain positions and time with respect to the EOD motor command (multimodal PFs) . Hence, the critical step is a nonlinearity in the response to position and timing signals such that only the conjunction of the two evokes a response. As shown here, precisely such an operation occurs in individual GCs that fire only at restricted body positions and times relative to the EOD motor command.”

Meanwhile, the mormyrid itself seems to throw it all on a heap and catches its prey.

[18] (Sawtell et al. 2008)

“Individual parallel fibers could convey EOCD information only, proprioceptive information only, or some mixture of the two. The fact that IPSPs were larger after pairing at both the paired and unpaired tail positions is consistent with efferent cells receiving a mixture of EOCD only and combined EOCD and proprioceptive parallel fibers.”

We will revisit this fish.

...

These observations should make us aware of the different relationships that 'modalities' can have relative to the DS and relative to each other.

We first might ask ourselves if a modality is 'relevant' : the possibility exists that it bears no relationship to the DS.

A correlation between such a modality (eventually in combination with others) and a DS would only start to arise when a novel situation or activity calls for it, and before that happens it only exists as a 'potentiality'.

Next - when different correlated modalities are available - it has to be evaluated if their combined use is just only 'reinforcing' (since interrelated) or if it is 'dimensional', i.e. they act as independent variables that specify kind of coordinates in an 'input-space'.

[19] (Chabrol et al. 2015)

“Our results show that GC responses to vestibular driver inputs are greatly enhanced when the visual supporting input is concurrently activated. This phenomenon, termed multisensory enhancement, has been reported in superior colliculus and neocortex as a mechanism to enhance saliency of stimuli as well as generating a unified percept from senses with inherently different psychophysical responses.”

These considerations are important when it comes to understanding how GrCs cope with these inputs.

...

Finally we must consider the 'dimensionality' of a system.

In mormyrid fish cancelling the ESD with GSs constructed with an EOCD and UBC prolongings, 'technically' one input line would suffice (the GS is stereotyped and always the same), and a 'delay line' of GrCs could have done the job when GrC(n) (shortly) activates GrC(n+1) when GrC(1) 'gets the signal' (but – of course - GrCs don't activate each other).

Each GrC would then contact an MGC on an apical dendrite with a plastic synapse, all MGCs receiving the DS via basal dendrites, and decorrelation could proceed.

In elasmobranch skates, simplifying breathing to a back-and-forth movement and having it represented by a proprioceptive code that can take say 10 values, 10 input lines (each representing one of the 10 'preferred values') each connected to one GrC would suffice.

...

In mormyrids, when in need to cancel the EOD-ESD for every tail position, the problem cannot be 'solved' with a one-dimensional line of GrCs : a 2D-grid is needed to accommodate for an (EOCD+UBC) axis and an independent proprioceptive axis.

A (say) 10 by 10 grid would be implemented with twice 10 MFs each having 10 terminals, together engaging a total of 100 GrCs that have 2 inputs each, with the GrCs performing AND-gating on these inputs.

Ideally these 100 GrCs should represent all possible combinations of the inputs.

Accepting such a combinatorial system of inputs for the GrCs, a specific GrC here would get a signal at input 1 indicating that the tail is at position x, and at input 2 indicating that it has - at that particular moment - 'licence to fire' (i.e. it is its turn in the timeslicing sequence).

Besides : it raises the question if UBCs are dedicated to one modality (the EOCD) and are not 'inserted' in MF-lines transmitting proprioceptive input - since this is silently assumed here - and if they would not be modality specific, does it spoil the purpose ?

...

In a 2D-system, GrCs must have at least 2 inputs (dendrites) to accommodate for the 'independent reference signals' but more inputs are allowed for extra reference signals that are interrelated with those already 'branched'.

As already noted, they introduce redundancy, but make the GS more robust and may guarantee continuity of function if a related signal should be absent for some reason (e.g. passive movement goes without MCCDs but proprioception is still there).

We may imagine an (x=y=z=10) 3D-system which would require three times 10 MFs each having 100 terminals, together engaging a total of 1000 GrCs that have at least 3 inputs each to accommodate 3 independent reference signals.

Fig. 6 from [20] (Gilmer et al. 2017)

We can ask ourselves if more-dimensional systems might exist and if that would still be 'practical' (Fig. 6).

[21] (Spanne et al. 2013)

“The size of the space spanned by one such discretized input could be considered to be N . If we introduce another input or dimension to this space, it will become a square with size NN . By adding another input dimension, the space will become a cube with size NNN . Hence, the size of the input space grows exponentially with the number of input dimensions.”

“The exponential growth of the space spanned by all input dimensions and all the resulting implications are what Bellman coined as the curse of dimensionality.”

A special case has to be considered : sometimes a GS brought in by an MF is already a combination of two modalities, allowing for one input (dendrite) less (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7 from [21] (Spanne et al. 2013)

[22] (Huang et al. 2013)

“The proprioceptive pathway appears to be intersected by corollary discharges at multiple stages. Previously, corollary and sensory information has been shown to converge in the first stage of proprioceptive processing - in the precerebellar neurons of the spinal cord (Hongo and Okada, 1967; Hongo et al., 1967; Hantman and Jessell, 2010). The present findings indicate that one synapse further up the proprioceptive pathway - at cerebellar granule cells - this convergence occurs again.”

[23] (Ishikawa et al. 2015)

“Some granule cells appear to be unimodal, some have multisensory input delivered by separate mossy fibers, and some have multisensory input delivered by a single mossy fiber.”

[14] (Requarth et al. 2014)

“We found numerous mossy fibers within EGp that exhibited responses to both tectal microstimulation and passive tail displacements. The fraction of fibers exhibiting such mixed responses was approximately onethird in our experiments, although this is likely to be an underestimate.”

“The population of mixed mossy fibers recorded here likely corresponds to a lateral column system in the mormyrid spinal cord that shares a number of anatomical similarities with the mammalian ventral spinocerebellar tract (Szabo et al., 1990) . Mixed spinocerebellar pathways have been studied extensively in mammals (Oscarsson, 1965; Arshavsky et al., 1978; Hantman and Jessell, 2010; Jankowska et al., 2011; Fedirchuk et al., 2013; Spanne and Jörntell, 2013) .”

When MFs get their signal from a source in the associative areas of the cerebral cortex, then I assume that they carry a signal that is 'by definition' the result of the integration of several 'primary' modalities.

...

The actual A-path produced by the GSs is to be viewed as one-dimensional, but when there is a coordinate system built from independent modalities, then the A-path is to be seen as a path 'chosen' in a 2D, 3D ..., landscape, with the possibility of bifurcations, and alternative routes to go from A to B, etc. 'as the fish chooses how to waggle its tail'.

[16] (Requarth et al. 2014)

“The number and variety of sensory patterns evoked by movements is far greater than the sensory patterns resulting from the EOD, raising the question of the capacity of ELL neurons to generate and simultaneously store multiple negative images appropriate to cancel sensory consequences of different movements.”

“Given the diversity of graded motor signals observed in mossy fibers together with the fact that each MG cell receives ~20,000 parallel fiber inputs and that ~30 MG cells converge onto each output cell (Bell et al., 2005; Meek et al., 1996), we expect that many more negative images could be stored.”

Each coordinate system, be it one- or more-dimensional, can be said to define an 'input space', and I will call each particular one an 'input space unit' [ISU].

We might 'describe' an ISU with shorthand like this : (ab)(cd)(e) where each letter stands for a participating modality, and where the parentheses group those modalities that are interrelated.

Hence, (ab)(cd)(e) would mean that this particular ISU is 3D and that GrCs belonging to it can receive 3 to 5 modalities for inputs as follows : ace, ade, bce, bde, abce, abde, acde, bcde and abcde.

...

The mormyrid of Sawtell uses an (EOCD+UBC)(proprioception) 2D-ISU to counter an ESD caused by a tail-modulated EOD, but it does the same for other body parts such as fins, trunk and chin-appendage.

[17] (Sawtell 2010)

“EGp GCs receive excitatory input from MFs including electric organ corollary discharge (EOCD) signals related to the timing of the motor command to discharge the electric organ and proprioceptive signals conveying information about the position of the tail, trunk, fins, and flexible chin appendage.”

“A total of 134 units were obtained that exhibited tonic firing that was unrelated to the timing of the EOD motor command. In a large majority of these units (123 of 134), baseline firing could be strongly modulated by proprioceptive stimuli, i.e., passive displacements of the tail (n = 81), trunk (n = 33), chin appendage (n = 5), or ipsilateral pectoral fin (n = 4) .”

On top of that - and against the advice of Sawtell – remember

[17] (Sawtell 2010)

“In short, PF inputs that represent either body position or motor command timing (proprioceptive and EOCD PFs) will lead to plastic changes at a specific position but at all times or at a specific time but at all positions. Clearly, a simple addition of such changes will not lead to plastic changes restricted to both position and time. Restricting plastic changes to certain positions and times requires PF inputs with activity confined to certain positions and time with respect to the EOD motor command (multimodal PFs). Hence, the critical step is a nonlinearity in the response to position and timing signals such that only the conjunction of the two evokes a response. As shown here, precisely such an operation occurs in individual GCs that fire only at restricted body positions and times relative to the EOD motor command.”

the mormyrid still puts a lot of resources into a 1D-ISU with the EOCD+UBC alone - and that shows up in ESD-cancellation graphs that are a bit less than perfect.

[17] (Sawtell 2010)

“Likewise, depression of PF(-PuC synapse)s conveying EOCD information without proprioceptive signals (EOCD PFs) cannot account for the position-specific changes that were observed. A depression of EOCD PF(-PuC synapse)s could, however, explain the small, temporally specific reduction in MG cell responses that was often observed across all body positions after pairing. The absence of temporally specific potentiation at body positions at which broad spikes were paired at long delays can also be explained by an overall depression of EOCD PFs that masked concurrent potentiation of multimodal PFs.”

[18] (Sawtell et al. 2008)

“It is also important to note that although they were reduced, effects of tail position on E- and I-cell responses were not entirely absent.”

Hence, in the case of the ELL we discern ISUs like (a) and (a)(b) where a=EOCD+UBC and b=proprioception of the tail, but there is the likely presence of (a)(c) and (a)(d) with c being proprioception of a fin, and d being proprioception of the chin appendage.

[17] (Sawtell 2010)

“The fish’s own movements alter the relative positions of electroreceptors (located on the flexible chin appendage, head, and trunk) and the electric organ (located in the tail), resulting in large changes in electroreceptor firing (Engelmann et al., 2008; Sawtell and Williams, 2008).”

Since movements of tail, fins, chin appendage all can be considered independent of each other, the ideal ISU that would permit complete ESD-cancellation in all possible situations should be of the form (a)(b)(c)(d)

[17] (Sawtell 2010)

“Sparse coding might allow for the generation of predictions appropriate to cancel electrosensory input associated with quite specific events (e.g., a particular configuration of the body involving tail, trunk, and chin appendage at the time of the EOD motor command)”

Such a multi-D ISU however has the disadvantage that, as dimensions are added, input space grows exponentially, gobbling up too much resources.

Moreover, the multi-D ISU can only express its specificity if less-dimensional ISUs with the same modalities (ruining that specificity) are excluded.

If - in evolution - a more-dimensional ISU is to develop out from lesser-dimensional ones, we cannot expect the latter to disappear 'at once', hence mixtures will be likely.

So, the mormyrids seem to choose pragmatically for a 1D ISU to cancel the gross ESD and for adding several 2D ISUs (some are only important for local or 'foveal' regions) to partially correct for the movement effects on the electroreception system.

It surely is already an improvement, and maybe, Sawtell argues, it might not be in the interest of the fish to mute the tail-effect altogether, and does it use its tail by 'listening to it' to probe even better its environment.

[18] (Sawtell et al. 2008)

“The preceding discussion and analysis have considered changes in electrosensory input resulting from tail movements as a form of self-generated noise. Indeed, on average, the electrosensory consequences of tail movements are unlikely to convey useful information about the environment. It remains possible, however, that systematic changes in tail position, as are common during exploratory behavior, could alter the fish’s electrical field in such a way as to enhance the electrical images of nearby objects.”

“During probing behavior fish often approach an object tail first, bringing the electric organ in close proximity to the object.”

...

CONCLUSION

Several 'types' of GSs were reviewed : after the time-fixed GS that must do with an announcing signal and inventive use of UBCs, we encounter the time- and state-correlated GSs which have a causal connection with the unwanted ESD, making them easily reproducible. GSs are said here to be based on 'reference signals'.

Modalities can be 'classified' by the type of information they represent, but their mutual relations are to be considered, and when the tail-wagging mormyrid is examined, GSs are uncovered that introduce 'dimensionality' by using independent modalities.

While GSs may be derived from 'meaningful' sources, their 'intrinsic meaningful signal content' is lost in the process and it was not even destined to be 'processed'. Just their 'physical format' and their combined use is to make GrCs to fire at the right moments.

So, while combining two or more interrelated modalities can make GSs more 'robust', combining two or more independent modalities is needed to be able to produce 2D, 3D ... sets of A-paths where each one is adapted for a particular situation

An A-path is to be seen as a path taken in a 'landscape' or - more generically - an 'input space', defined by a coordinate system, and each such input space - an ISU - contains the 'nodes' defined by its coordinates, but increasing dimensionality leads to exponential growth of needed resources (GrCs ...).

Coexistence of (n)D-ISUs with (n-1)D-ISUs almost seems inevitable, as shown in the mormyrid, and although this should ruin the specificity of (n)D-ISUs, it does not prevent the fish from 'performing' relatively close to perfection.

...

E) INPUT LOAD VARIABILITY

Abbreviations used in this section :

A-path	Activation path	GrL	Granular layer (or EGp in CB-like structures)
AP	Action potential	ILF	The input load factor
APFV	The activated parallel fiber volume	ILF-VP	The ILF variability problem
AS	the activating signal	ILFMAX	The maximum value the ILF can take
ASS	Activating signal strength	LFuC	Large fusiform cell
ApO	Apical output	LGC	Large ganglion cell
B-spike	Broad spike	MGC	Medium ganglion cell
BIE	The backpropagating integration effect	MG1C	Type 1 MGC
CC	The correlated component	MG2C	Type 2 MGC
	iCC	N-spike	Narrow spike
D	Depress / Depression	P	Potentiate / Potentiation
DS	The signal to be decorrelated	PF	Parallel fiber
	aDS	PriC	Principal cell
	iDS	PuC	Purkinje(like) cell
	iaDS	SS	Synapse strength
ELL	Electrosensory lateral line lobe	aSS	The actual SS
EPSP	Excitatory postsynaptic potential	UC	The uncorrelated component
GS	Guiding signal	iUC	The inverted UC
GrC	Granule cell	VP	Variability problem

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

Silently - in the demo plasticity formula - 'synapse strength' (SS) and 'signal value' were considered to be equivalent entities that can be added, subtracted ..., but in reality SS represents a gain factor with which the presynaptic signal strength (the ASS or the 'Activating signal strength' - don't confuse with aSS) is to be multiplied.

Spikes of the AS can be treated more or less as 'signals with unity value', but when they arrive in bursts at the PF-PuC synapse they certainly cause a 'variability problem' [VP] if a time-window mechanism that allows for integration of more than one spike is at play at the postsynaptic side.

When viewing the A-path as 'a string of synapse populations', activated in sequence, we have to consider the issue that those populations can differ in volume : say, one timeslice can have 5 synapses 'allocated' to it, another 10, etc., and I will call this factor 'the APFV or the 'Activated PF Volume'.

Both ASS and APFV have a similar effect : a synapse hit by a burst of spikes (time window allowing), or several 'parallel' synapses (lying on as much PFs but on the same PuC) each receiving one spike.

...

I will embrace ASS and APFV in one concept : the Input Load Factor [ILF], and I will refer to the VP it creates as the ILF-VP.

Hence remember that the ILF is always to be understood as consisting of two components : a 'local' ILF due to the ASS, and a 'global' ILF due to the APFV.

I get the impression that in many a model, the ILF is simply set to 'unity', thereby evading the ILF-VP.

To solve it we might consider upstream control of the ASS (making it a constant across synapses), and control of the amount of active PFs (keeping activated synapse population volumes constant across timeslices).

However, a closer look at the neurocircuitry of the ELL will reveal that it might harbour another mechanism that deals with the ILF-VP.

...

In the mormyromast region of the ELL the basilar dendrites of principal cells [PriCs] receive a spike burst coded DS derived from electrosensory afferent fibers, and this DS apparently is no part of the input to the granular mass from which PFs arise that cross the apical dendrite trees of these cells.

[24] (Roberts et al. 2002)

"The representation of the electric field strength as latency (pulse coding) would be highly sensitive to information losses due to noise as the information passes through synaptic junctions. As the electrosensory information passes through the first stage of sensory processing, the deep granule layer of the ELL, the signal converges with inputs from central sources that convey timing information about when the EOD occurred. The convergence of these two inputs is thought to be translated via granule cells that act as coincidence detectors and relay a burst of spikes where the number of spikes depends on the time difference between the EOD and the afferent spike. When the sensory information reaches the principal cells of the ganglion layer, much of the timing code is lost and a rate coding can be identified."

MGCs generate - apart from 'standard' or normal 'narrow' spikes' [N-spikes] - also so-called 'broad spikes' [B-spikes] that propagate into the apical dendrites where the Ca⁺⁺ surges they provoke are necessary for plasticity to occur, in analogy with what CFs do.

[25] (Roberts et al. 2010)

"Medium ganglion cells respond to a depolarizing input with two types of spikes: a small narrow spike and a large, broad spike that is generated at a higher threshold than the narrow spike and mediates synaptic plasticity. Experimental evidence suggests that the small spike is axonal and the broad spike propagates into the dendrites (Grant et al. 1998)."

[26] (Sawtell et al. 2007)

"Several lines of evidence suggest that B spikes are initiated in the soma or proximal dendrites and actively propagate through the molecular layer in MG cell apical dendrites."

[27] (Grant et al. 1998)

"A large and unusually broad spike is recorded inside medium ganglion cells, and field potential responses suggest that this spike is propagated into the apical dendrites."

"The broad spike is necessary for anti-Hebbian associative synaptic plasticity at the parallel fiber to medium ganglion cell synapse (Bell et al., 1993; C. Bell, V. Han, Y. Sugawara, and K. Grant, unpublished data)."

These B-spikes are fired once the membrane potential at the B-spike trigger zone crosses threshold (while N-spikes fire already at a lower threshold), and this potential (as assumed in the model of Roberts) is determined by the algebraic summation - at the MGC-soma - of the apical and basilar dendritic outputs that converge on it (I will consequently call it 'outputs' - to distinguish it from the presynaptic inputs).

[27] (Grant et al. 1998)

"Most medium ganglion cells also showed a small, narrow spike (5-15 mV in amplitude, 1-2 msec in duration) that fired independently of the large, broad spike and had a lower threshold than the broad spike to intracellular or synaptic stimulation."

[28] (Roberts et al. 2000)

"The average membrane potential of the model ganglion cell is modulated by the sum of two sources of synaptic input, the basilar dendrites and the apical dendrites."

...

For the whole setup of PriCs to be meaningful for adaptive filtering, DS information coming in by the basilar dendrites should be transmitted into the apical dendrites to reach the site of plasticity, and that, most likely, is only feasible by way of active backpropagation, and hence by a spiking mechanism.

B-spikes most plausibly can deliver this info, coded by spike form and/or spike frequency.

[29] (Bell et al. 1997)

"Propagation of a spike into the apical dendrites would provide a mechanism of communication between the basilar parts of the cells where sensory inputs terminate and the apical dendrites where the parallel fibers terminate, allowing sensory and parallel fiber inputs to interact."

[25] (Roberts et al. 2010)

"The dendritic spike would inform the parallel fiber synapses of strong depolarization caused by afferent sensory input to the basilar dendrites and mediates plasticity at the synapses from the PF to the MG cells."

[27] (Grant et al. 1998)

"The breadth of the broad spike could have functional significance in allowing voltage-sensitive calcium channels to remain open longer, or in relieving the voltage block of NMDA channels for a longer period of time."

[30] (Roberts et al. 2003)

"If the time window within which averages are computed is made smaller and approaches millisecond or sub-millisecond durations, then a spike-rate based rule becomes indistinguishable from a spike-timing based rule."

Overlap (the intersection) of the B-spike (Ca⁺⁺) wave and the presynaptic spike wave is a condition for plasticity to occur (hence called 'associative'), as if the presynaptic spike opens a short time window during which Ca⁺⁺ released by the B-spike can substantiate plastic changes.

[31] (Roberts 1999)

"In these types of learning rules, the presence and direction of synaptic change depends on the precise timing of pre- and postsynaptic spikes during the association period. The asymmetry is thought to result from the dynamics of long-term potentiation (or depression) mediated by glutamate receptors of the NMDA-type [Debanne et al., 1994, Gustafsson et al., 1987, Levy and Steward, 1983] . Because these receptors require the binding of glutamate in conjunction with postsynaptic depolarization for the influx of Ca²⁺ ions, the associated changes in synaptic efficacy occur if the postsynaptic depolarization follows the beginning of the epsp."

The B-spike info is meant to be a parameter for the weight changes of synapses which are activated presynaptically at the particular timeslice when the B-spike occurs.

...

When considering the type 1 MGC [MG1C], we see that the basilar input (the DS) is inverted (becoming the iDS) by an inhibiting interneuron and hence its membrane potential can be said to represent the subtraction of the DS from the MG1C apical output.

[28] (Roberts et al. 2000)

"Due to inhibitory interneurons in the deep layers of the ELL, the afferent signal is often inverted in the MG cells, as in the simulations."

[32] (Bell et al. 2008)

"Some of the interneurons of the deep layers are inhibitory, allowing for a change of sign, whereby excitation in the periphery is converted into inhibition of some principal cells."

Let's consider step by step how the 'basic' formula has to be rewritten to integrate these observations.

The formula $Next\ SS = aSS - aSS * x\% + aDS * x\%$ in principle allows for plasticity to be implemented by P and D signalling cascades that occur in parallel (simultaneously).

It takes for granted however that the DS proper can be used as a value inserted in the formula, while in the ELL the signals coming through these synapses first merge with the iDS at the MGC soma and the integrated result is then sent back (not the DS), the B-spike being its carrier - a form of intraneuronal feedback.

The demo formula allows for that since we can rewrite it as :

$Next\ SS = aSS - (aSS - aDS) * x\%$ in which we recognise the subtraction operation.

...

In the subtraction the information of the component terms is lost, prohibiting simultaneous P and D plasticity, but P or D plasticity cascades that depend on the sign of the subtraction result are still a possible option (D when +, P when -).

(Strictly considered, the aSS term is still locally available, allowing recalculation of the aDS term out of the subtraction, but that looks a bit cumbersome).

Even if this formula with its 'single x' seems to say mathematically that with the subtraction strategy p% automatically has to equal d%, we need to be aware that - biologically - P and D will always have different implementation mechanisms, and hence the balancing between the two remains a real issue.

When all signals are 'lifted into the positive' the sign reversal can be physically correlated with a critical Ca⁺⁺ level, which on the low side enables P and on the high side enables D.

Note that - with the introduction of 'inverted' signals (iDS being -DS) - I will use the term 'algebraic summation' instead of 'subtraction', where I believe it is appropriate.

...

The next change is to replace the aSS term in the subtraction part (aSS - aDS) with SUM(ApO) .

SUM(ApO) represents the summing of the excitatory postsynaptic potentials [EPSPs] (not just the SSs) of all the simultaneously activated synapses (which I already called 'parallel' synapses), and the result of the algebraic summation with the basilar output (the iaDS) – done at the soma - is what is fed back to the local apical sites.

Hence the formula now is : $Next\ SS = aSS - [SUM(ApO) + iaDS] * x\%$.

...

In the demo program itself I do not bother about 'summing', considering that – at the soma - the effect of x parallel synapses will be equivalent to attributing an x times greater 'input load' to just one particular synapse (the ASS at that synapse). So, in-program, SUM(ApO) will be represented by aSS*ILF .

Remember : the ILF combines the effect of different ASSs across synapses and of different APFVs across timeslices (the amount of synchronously firing GrCs activating PF-PuC synapses).

At the start of a 'run', the demo program will - for every particular synapse - randomly pick a value between 1 and a chosen maximum for the variability range of it [ILFMAX], and assign it to it, so that this ILF value stays the same for each particular synapse over all iterations, but will differ across synapses.

It is NOT to be confused with 'ambient noise' that - in vivo - can affect the AS (I provide no room for stochastic noise in the demo program), but it is meant to reflect that each GrC, when it is its turn to fire in the sequence of an A-path, is always supposed to be triggered by the same input combination, resulting in the same output characteristics at each iteration, but these input combinations (the GSs) - and hence output characteristics (the AS) – can differ from one GrC to another.

...

When ILFMAX=1 then ILF=1 for all synapses, and there is no variability, but when ILFMAX is say 2 it means that the ILF of each synapse is a value picked between 1 and 2, etc. .

With a different ILF for each synapse, it will show in the demos as a 'hairy' appearance of the histograms, and as a 'shower' of dots of the 'skylines', settling to 'normal' when the formula is successful in decorrelating it out.

Let's have a look at how the adapted formula 'performs' : see Fig. 8, in which ILFMAX=10 and hence the ILF can have a value between 1 and 10 (! - far more than I expect it to be in vivo).

Fig. 8 <https://www.dropbox.com/s/bt7nfadu747v07q/demo-1-26.mp4?dl=0>

It demonstrates more specifically that the strategy of the MGCs (integrating apical and basilar output first, then adjusting weights according to the result) makes the decorrelation process independent of varying ASSs and of varying APFVs.

In other words : if a specific synapse should receive consistently 'double input load', it will settle for a weight that is only half the value compared to when it would have received 'unity load'.

And since the ILF*aSS products of all parallel synapses will be summed they also will settle for weights that compensate for their summed contributions.

I will call this effect, consequence of the B-spike mechanism (and the intraneuronal feedback) here, the 'backpropagating integration effect' [BIE].

It solves the ILF-VP.

...

The S4 histogram now reflects the timeslice 'apical outputs' which together should converge to represent the CC of the DS (NOT of the iDS that came in through the basilar dendrites !).

This CC annuls the iCC in the iDS, generating the iUC, which - MG1C being an inhibiting cell - is inverted to an UC when delivered to the Large Fusiform cell [LFuC].

And - logically then - an MG2C receiving a DS proper (not inverted) will sculpt synapses such that they will output iCC, annulling the CC in the DS, generating the UC, which - MG2C being inhibiting too, delivers an iUC to the Large Ganglion cell [LGC].

...

This 'independence from ASS and APFV' comes almost as a relief, since otherwise it would have been a burden for the GrL to constrain ASSs and APFVs to near constants.

The ILF variability nonetheless goes with a small but acceptable cost in decorrelation precision, comparable to the raising of p% and d% values as shown in the early demos.

The BIE offers a solution that lies 'outside' the GrL, but it does not preclude the existence of processes inside the GrL intended to 'stabilize' the ILF.

...

Mathematically the original formula 'solves' the ILF-VP too : it is equivalent even when it does not 'isolate' a subtraction between brackets, but physiologically it makes an essential difference if a 'subtraction' is implemented or not.

In the ELL clearly there is a subtraction (algebraic summation) performed at the MGC-soma, the result of which is delivered postsynaptically by the B-spike at the plasticity sites, but the ILF-VP will resurface in situations where there is no B-spike

Replacing aSS with aSS*ILF in the formula also shifts its meaning : physiologically it now primarily aims at adapting the ApO (but implementing it by adapting the SS) - and S4 will always represent aSS*ILF, being equivalent to aSS only when ILF is unity.

...

CONCLUSION

Attention is drawn to the fact that

- 1) 'synapse strength' is not to be equated with a 'signal' since it is only a gain factor to be multiplied with a presynaptic signal strength, and that
- 2) 'in population view' the allocation of variable amounts of synapses ("parallel synapses") to different timeslices may pose a problem with similar effect.

Both effects are taken together under the concept 'Input Load Factor' and the problem caused by the variability of the ILF across synapses is called the 'ILF variability problem'.

While we may wonder if the GrL has means to control the ILF variability across synapses, the demo plasticity formula (or learning rule) itself seems to make no provision for modulations in presynaptic signals nor for different loads of 'parallel synapses', but a closer look at CB-like neurocircuitry seems to give a clue to a solution.

Reviewing what is known of MGCs in the ELL, there might be a 'backpropagating integration effect' (BIE) - implemented by an algebraic summation process engaging a B-spike and hence associative plasticity rules – and it favours a P and D dependent on a segregating Ca-threshold, replacing the earlier simultaneous P and D.

Most importantly, the BIE is also identified as a mechanism that solves the ILF-VP : differences in AS strength across synapses and differences in the number of simultaneously activated synapses across timeslices (the APFV) are

compensated for in the weights of the involved synapses, but a role for the GrL to attenuate these differences already upstream is still a possibility.

The Next SS = aSS - aSS * x% + aDS * x% formula is transformed into

Next SS = aSS - (aSS - aDS) * x% reflecting the apical-basilar integration, and into

Next SS = aSS - [SUM(ApO) + iaDS] * x% (though remaining in-program Next SS = aSS - [aSS*ILF + iaDS] * x%), introducing an ILF ('capturing' both ASS and APFV) that can vary across synapses (with a variability range limited in-program by a chosen ILFMAX value).

A demo shows that decorrelation still stands even under heavily varying ILF across synapses.

...

F) WRONG ADDRESSING - CORRELATED

Abbreviations used in this section :

A-path	Activation path	GrL	Granular layer (or EGP in CB-like structures)
APFV	The activated parallel fiber volume	ILF	The input load factor
AS	Activating signal	ILF-VP	The ILF variability problem
ASS	Activating signal strength	MF	mossy fiber
CB-like	Cerebellum-like	P	Potentiate / Potentiation
CC	The correlated component	PF	Parallel fiber
D	Depress / Depression	PuC	Purkinje(like) cell
DS	The signal to be decorrelated	RTL	The relevant timelapse
ELL	Electrosensory lateral line lobe	SS	Synapse strength
EOCD	Electric organ corollary discharge	aSS	The actual SS
EOD	Electric organ discharge	UC	The uncorrelated component
ESD	Electrosensory disturbance	VP	Variability problem
FFI	Feedforward inhibition	WA	Wrong addressing
GS	Guiding signal	CWA	Correlated WA
GrC	Granule cell	UBC	Unipolar brush cell

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

Which factors have a potential for corrupting an A-path and hence PuC output signal quality ?

Noise , of course, comes into mind first, but as long as it is totally random - uncorrelated with the DS - it will for a large part be 'decorrelated out', as the demos with jitter added to the signal showed.

Other factors are structural, and need to be identified and assessed for their impact on the decorrelation process.

...

In the case of the mormyrid ELL it was already noted that UBCs might pose a 'reproducibility hazard'.

Reproducibility is absolutely necessary because the averaging process depends on iterating many times through the same A-path (using the same GSs).

Therefore, when UBCs are 'responsible' for generating GSs, their output sequence should be the same at every iteration, timelocked to the ESD, while the only signal providing a time reference seems to be the EOCD at the start (gunshotlike in the mormyrid).

It is to be expected that timelocking gets less precise (diverges) with time evolving , and that puts a time limit to the reproducibility performance. Mauk and Donegan - though again in the context of conditioning - describe it well :

[33] (Mauk et al. 1997)

“Why then does the ability of the CS to support conditioning decline as the ISI increases ?

This may reflect an inherent tendency for small amounts of inconsistency early in the CS to be amplified into large amounts of inconsistency in later portions of the CS (see Lorenz 1963) . This tendency could arise from the way in which the activity of each cell at any given time is determined by previous activity in many other cells.

A spurious spike in a granule cell may subsequently lead to spurious activity in Golgi cells that, given the divergence of their projections, could then lead to even more spurious activity (or lack of activity) in other granule cells. Thus, the degradation in consistency produced by a uniform noise source can accumulate and lead to a time-dependent decrease in the across-trials consistency of the neurons activated by a CS. The sources of noise could be as subtle as the statistical nature of transmitter release and ion channel openings/closings.”

I will define 'the relevant timelapse' [RTL] as the period during which a corrective signal should be able to cancel an ESD properly, since it is to be expected that - towards the end - averages will get 'smeared out' over neighbouring timeslices, causing less cancellation precision : UBCs should be able 'to hold it out' for an RTL of some 50 to 200 ms.

[34] (Requarth 2014)

“Previous work in mormyrid fish shows that ELL principal cells generate temporally-specific predictions as long as 200 ms after the EOD motor command. It is known that CD responses in MFs appear to be extremely brief and restricted to a short delay after the EOD motor command. Thus, GC circuitry must temporally expand CD signals into a format appropriate for sensory cancellation.”

[35] (Sawtell et al. 2010)

“Most electrosensory processing is likely to occur within 20–50 ms after the EOD motor command.”

[36] (Roberts et al. 2000)

“Pairing the electric organ command signal with an electrosensory stimulus for a few minutes results in the development of a response to the command alone that is a negative image of the previously paired response to the sensory stimulus [Bell and Szabo, 1986] . The negative image is a kind of prediction about expected sensory input that is specific to the time course of the sensory response (which lasts about 100 msec in the ampullary region) and its polarity (excitation or inhibition) .”

However, when 'statelocking' (cfr the use of proprioceptive input) comes into the place of timelocking, the reproducibility issue poses no problem any more.

[37] (Manto et al. 2011)

“An orderly succession of states may serve as “trigger points” during the production of a skilled movement, even though the overall rate of the movement may vary from one instantiation to the next. Models in which the cerebellum is viewed as a state estimator highlight how this structure imposes temporal regularities with relative rather than absolute timing.”

...

But maybe reproducibility can afford a certain measure of randomness as long as it does not come into conflict with the requirement of 'uniqueness'.

That is : uniqueness is the requirement that a GrC does not fire more than once during the RTL, but if the GrC does NOT fire at every iteration, then no harm is done. It does not degrade the build-up of correct averages at the dependent PF-PuC synapses, but only slows it down a bit.

[38] (Kennedy et al. 2014)

This choice was motivated by the observation that the probability of spike firing varied widely across recorded late mossy fibers (unlike the other response classes, which fired after every command) .

...

Uniqueness by itself is trickier : every synapse should be bound to one specific DS-timeslice, and when - during the RTL - this synapse nonetheless gets involved with other timeslices, its averaging process is compounded, degrading decorrelation quality.

A PF-PuC synapse is related to one specific PF and one specific GrC, and hence this synapse cannot be 'activated' by another GrC.

If this synapse is activated more than once during the RTL, it must be due to a GS which is not specific enough (meaning that the same combination of inputs is presented to the GrC more than once during the RTL) or it must be due to failing 'AND-gating' by the GrC, which then will be triggered into firing at several of the unique GS input combinations.

...

I used the (basic) demo program again to visualize the effects.

Each synapse - representing a timeslice - will now not only 'receive' its normal (time-related) DS-timeslice value, but also a number of other DS-timeslice values, picked at random out of the whole DS (S3 in the demo).

Since the DS - as well 'in silico' as in vivo - is processed timeslice by timeslice, a 'wrong timing issue' can be reformulated as a 'wrong addressing issue' : it can be interpreted that the timeslice DS value of the moment is not only 'delivered' at its due (synapse) address, but also at other addresses picked at random out of the A-path (which is a string of addresses) – see Fig. 9.

Fig. 9

Normally we have :

	T1	T2	T3
S1	DS1		
S2		DS2	
S3			DS3

Read it as follows :

Synaps 1 (S1) is postsynaptically confronted with the first timeslice of the DS (DS1) when GrC1 (bound to S1) fires at time 1 (T1) and activates S1 presynaptically.

Formulated shorter : S1 gets DS1 when GrC1 fires at T1,

S2 ...,
S3 ...

But now we have e.g. : GrC1 fires at T1 and T3, GrC2 fires at T1 and T2, GrC3 fires at T3

	T1	T2	T3
S1	DS1		DS3
S2	DS1	DS2	
S3			DS3

Read horizontally :

S1 gets DS1 and DS3 since GrC1 fires at T1, but does so (wrongly) also at T3
 S2 gets DS1 and DS2 since GrC2 fires at T2, but does so (wrongly) also at T1
 S3 gets DS3 since GrC3 fires at T3

Which you can also read (vertically) as a wrong addressing (WA) issue :

DS1 is addressed to S1 but also (wrongly) to S2
 DS2 is addressed to S2
 DS3 is addressed to S3 but also (wrongly) to S1

There is a restriction to respect however : reproducibility being considered intact, the same 'wrong addresses' picked at random at the first iteration must be used again at all the following iterations.

Indeed, the GSs are presumed to be identical at every iteration, and when it results in AS 'mistakes', it will do so faithfully again at every iteration.

...

As expected, we see decorrelation degrade as the number of 'wrong addresses' per right one increases (observe S4 flattening). Compare with the result of a 'clean run' : Figs. 10 a-d

Fig. 10

a : no wrong addressings

b : 1 wrong for every 1 right

c : 2 wrong for every 1 right

d : 5 wrong for every 1 right

10a : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/yp9xx5ahb0mcqge/demo-1-8.mp4?dl=0>

10b : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/ftby8lg26wpk7rh/demo-1-17.mp4?dl=0>

10c : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/ykkadbp20oeq56/demo-1-18.mp4?dl=0>

10d : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/pjsi3o1kwx0kcf9/demo-1-19.mp4?dl=0>

We can only conclude that repetitive firing of GrCs during the RTL is to be avoided as much as possible.

I will refer to this problem type as a 'Wrong addressing problem' or WA problem. More specifically, we have here a 'correlated WA' [CWA] problem, since the same WAs occur at each iteration through the DS.

...

Again, for UBCs, it is to be established by goal oriented in vivo research that all GrCs involved in the firing sequence fire only once during the RTL (as is assumed in many a model), since otherwise a CWA problem is created.

[39] (Williams et al. 2013)

“Each presynaptic cell i spikes exactly once at a fixed time within each sweep of the repeated external input, causing a corresponding postsynaptic potential response (PSP) in the postsynaptic cell.”

For the same reason, the prolonged firing observed in UBCs also better not results in prolonged firing of GrCs (grouping timeslices).

Feedforward inhibition [FFI] by Golgi cells certainly is a mechanism that keeps the firing of GrCs short, but is it enough ? AND-gating by itself will also tend to shorten GrC firing : if a GrC only fires when all the specific parameter values are to be present at its inputs, the duration of firing will tend to be very short since cut-off will occur when just one of those inputs 'goes low' - and that is expected to happen quickly in a dynamic system.

In an 'UBC environment' the connection of different types of UBCs (like ON- and OFF-type UBCs) to AND-gating GrCs might have a similar effect.

[40] (Borgess et al. 2015)

“This study reveals two classes of UBC that differ strikingly in their response to mossy-fiber input. The first displayed an inward, biphasic EPSC, similar to the EPSC characterized in cerebellar UBCs (Rossi et al., 1995, Kinney et al., 1997) . This ON subtype was mGluR1alpha+ and showed an immediate prolonged increase in firing frequency due to a slow EPSC mediated by both AMPARs and mGluR1alfa. The OFF subtype had a small inward AMPAR component that was overwhelmed by a larger, slow outward current that paused intrinsic firing, and in some cases led to delayed, rebound firing.”

The ideal mechanism should make GrCs unreactive to further stimulation after they have fired, and should 'reset' them when the RTL has passed.

...

When the GSs are state-correlated (and with AND-gating assumed not to fail), the occurrence of repetitive GrC firing would mean that the GSs reflect a state previously already encountered e.g. when the GSs consist only of position coordinates and a movement causes passage through the same position twice but from another direction.

We could say that the A-path intersects with itself in this situation, and the intersection point (just one point though) is prone to averaging two different timeslices.

Adding the direction as an independent modality (dimension) in the GSs can solve the problem by having the A-path crossing itself, instead of intersecting.

...

CONCLUSION

The concept of the A-path and its requirements is revisited, but now focusing on factors that are deleterious to these requirements.

Resolution can be inadequate, but reproducibility can fail and uniqueness can be violated, leading in both cases to 'wrong addressing' issues, which are problematic by causing 'timeslice compounding' (averaging of signal values belonging to different timeslices) and this occurs when - during the RTL - GrCs fire more than once.

UBCs can be prone to 'time-locking-slip' (research on their discipline and endurance is necessary), and when state-locked, A-paths may intersect with themselves (while they better should cross).

GrCs NOT firing at every iteration is a tolerable exception to the reproducibility requirement (it only slows down the decorrelation speed), but firing more than once (during the RTL) AND reproducing it faithfully at every iteration is a CWA problem that is devastating for the decorrelation of the DS.

...

G) WRONG ADDRESSING - UNCORRELATED

Abbreviations used in this section :

A-path	Activation path	P	Potentiate / Potentiation
AS	Activating signal	PF	Parallel fiber
CC	The correlated component	PuC	Purkinje(like) cell
D	Depress / Depression	RTL	The relevant timelapse
DS	The signal to be decorrelated	UC	The uncorrelated component
ELL	Electrosensory lateral line lobe	WA	Wrong addressing
GS	Guiding signal	CWA	Correlated WA
GrC	Granule cell	UWA	Uncorrelated WA

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

When adapting the demo program to 'visualize' the WA problem, I first 'forgot' to ensure that the same mistakes occurred at every iteration, and – 'playing with the parameters' (the p%) - see what it gave in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11 : compare left and right (focus on S4)

a : 1 wrong for every 1 right with p=d=2%

b : 1 wrong for every 1 right with p=4% and d=2%

11a : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/v6p9dqhypjkz39v/demo-1-21.mp4?dl=0>

11b : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/c0m71o2ingssb85/demo-1-22.mp4?dl=0>

11c : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/yh0mbxj2117qpe0/demo-1-23.mp4?dl=0>

11d : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/bnppo89h5cefflo/demo-1-24.mp4?dl=0>

It appeared that p% :

must be doubled in the case of 2 addressings (one right and one wrong) per timeslice, and must be tripled in the case of 3 addressings (one right and two wrong) per timeslice, and so on, if decorrelation quality is to be restored.

One can observe S4 flattening when more addressings are wrong, and the trend is reversed when P is adjusted adequately (the 'fit' itself is no more representative in the videos).

...

When complying for reproducibility, with WA-mistakes occurring in each cycle at the same moments, correlated with the DS, the DS looks 'distorted' to the decorrelation procedure and hence a distorted CC and UC will be the outcome.

With a really random and uncorrelated distribution of WAs there is still distortion, but - after enough iterations - all synapses will be affected by more or less the same load of wrong DS-timeslice values, a load which converges, when averaged, to an average taken over the whole DS.

The contribution of the steadfast right timeslice value is still integrated in the averaging but it will appear to be reduced by a factor equal to the number of addressings (right + wrong), and having p% adjusted upwards with the same factor is one strategy to compensate for it.

This 'uncorrelated' WA [UWA] problem type is to be opposed to its correlated version or the CWA-problem type.

Whenever a kind of noise is introduced that proves to have no correlation at all with the DS - in other words : is perfectly random in relation to it - then the system, by virtue of its primary mission of decorrelation should be able to filter it out.

But does a UWA problem really exist in vivo ? I see no way how - in vivo - to get rid of the restriction that the same WA mistakes are bound to be repeated at every iteration : it is hardwired since each specific GrC will - on average - produce the same output under the same input conditions.

Hence, I tended to regard the UWA-demo as 'unrealistic'. And yet, if we think about it, the UWA-problem must exist, and very prominently indeed !

...

While I figure the CWAs to be mostly a problem of GrCs activating a PF-PuC synapse twice or more during the RTL - compounding timeslices - I consider the main source of UWA to be all the active A-paths delivering ASs from all sorts of ongoing activities that have NO correlation with the local DS (but can be relevant for PuCs farther away along the PFs).

Note that the synapses involved here are NOT the same synapses as those related to the A-path of our DS, since it are synapses 'belonging' to other A-paths.

These synapses 'have no business here', and therefore I consider them as synapses with a 'wrong addressing', but their presence is not without sense : unless it were hardwired, the 'system' cannot know beforehand which activities will prove to be correlated with the local DS ... so it better 'throws in the lot' in search for them.

Let's – for now – state that the UWA problem is not simply to be solved by an adjustment of the P/D balance. In a later section we will see how the ELL might deal with it.

...

CONCLUSION

Two different types of WA are to be distinguished : correlated and uncorrelated (CWA and UWA), and both have very different causes.

CWA is caused by the GS not being 'unique' enough to guarantee that - during the RTL - all synapses belonging to the A-path have a unique relationship with only one specific timeslice of the DS, or is caused by GrCs failing to AND-gate the GS signals properly.

UWA is caused by PF 'traffic' unrelated to the local DS of the PuC, but these unrelated activated synapses undergo plasticity as well as the related ones, and affect the output of the PuC.

'In silico', and with the formula 'at hand', the UWA problem apparently can be solved by 'skewing' the P-D balance appropriately, but it will appear that the ELL might tackle the problem in a totally different way.

...

H) SIGNAL 'LIFTING' BY NON-ASSOCIATIVE POTENTIATION

Abbreviations used in this section :

A-path	Activation path	ILFMAX	The maximum value the ILF can take
ApO	Apical output	JLN	The juxtalobar nucleus
B-spike	Broad spike	MGC	Medium ganglion cell
BIE	The backpropagating integration effect	MG1C	Type 1 MGC
BSa	B-spike associative	MG2C	Type 2 MGC
CC	The correlated component	MR	The modulatory range
D	Depress / Depression	MRMAX	The widest MR encountered over many iterations
DS	The signal to be decorrelated	N-spike	Narrow spike
	aDS The actual DS	P	Potentiate / Potentiation
	iDS The inverted DS	na-P	non-associative P
	iaDS The inverted actual DS	PF	Parallel fiber
ELL	Electrosensory lateral line lobe	SS	Synapse strength
EOCD	Electric organ corollary discharge	aSS	the actual SS
EOD	Electric organ discharge	UBC	Unipolar brush cell
ESD	Electrosensory disturbance	UC	The uncorrelated component
GrL	Granular layer (or EGp in CB-like structures)	iUC	The inverted UC
ILF	The input load factor	VP	Variability problem
ILF-VP	The ILF variability problem		

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

The thresholded B-spike mechanism itself poses problems which deserve a closer look.

We have to consider that MGCs depend on the B-spikes to get DS-related information to the plasticity site, and hence no DS parameterized plasticity can take place without B-spikes occurring.

Hence, when $(\text{SUM}(\text{ApO}) + \text{iaDS}) \Rightarrow \text{B-threshold}$, the DS info is transmitted to the plasticity site, but when smaller and a fortiori when negative - it is not.

If $\text{SUM}(\text{ApO})=0$, the B-threshold is likely to truncate the DS, provided the DS is even capable of reaching the threshold, which seems outright impossible if inhibiting neurons stand at the basilar gates.

Hence the basilar output signal is to be 'lifted' above B-threshold in its entirety if it is to influence plasticity in the apical dendritic tree of the MGC in a meaningful way.

Disinhibition of other inhibiting neurons contacting the MGC offers no solution if there is no excitation in the first place, and excitation can only come via the apical and the basilar dendrites.

...

At first sight two options present themselves to solve the problem :

1) a P independent of the B-threshold - the 'non-associative' P [na-P] included in many a model - which gradually strengthens the ApO, raising $(\text{SUM}(\text{ApO}) + \text{iaDS})$ eventually above B-threshold.

2) the addition of an excitatory signal to the iDS (as the Juxtalobar Nucleus [JLN] input seems to do) :

[41] (Bell et al. 1997)

"The electric organ corollary discharge evoked a compound EPSP in these cells with an onset latency of 10-12 msec, an amplitude of 3-8 mV, and a duration of ~40 msec."

Crossing the threshold and triggering B-spikes should then activate a 'D-component' - a B-spike associative D [BSa-D] - to balance and check the na-P.

When we presume (which we should) that apical synapses - at the beginning of their career - start with minimal strength, then the second strategy is of no help since these synapses are not to be depressed 'into the negative'.

Hence, an na-P seems unavoidable.

...

If na-P is part of the game one should expect to observe denser synaptic growth in MG1Cs than in MG2Cs, given that $\text{SUM}(\text{ApO})$ must be considerably larger if it has to compensate for inverted (inhibitory) basilar output.

I found - in the articles I read - no observations pointing in this direction.

na-P is unrelenting and therefore B-spikes should occur with due regularity to counterbalance the unceasing drive to a maximum level.

This is not the case : although strengthening the ApO increases the membrane potential at the soma and hence should enhance B-spiking, it has been observed in vivo (e.g. by Sawtell) that B-spikes can be very infrequent, inhibited as they apparently can be by central influences which exclusively target the B-spike trigger zone.

[42] (Sawtell et al. 2007)

"MG cells also exhibit B spikes, which are much less frequent and much larger than N spikes."

"These experiments also demonstrate that B spikes need not occur on every command cycle to induce plasticity. This is of obvious functional importance given that B spikes are infrequent in vivo. We observed substantial changes in N-spike patterns resulting from on the order of 100 B spikes."

Another argument to 'discredit' na-P is given by

[43] (Roberts et al. 2003)

"One difficulty for LTD as an explanation for motor learning is that no physiological method has yet been found for reversing the pairing-induced depression. A non-associative potentiation of the parallel fiber evoked EPSP is elicited by high frequency stimulation of the fibers, but this potentiation is due to a presynaptic increase in transmitter release and thus can not reverse the postsynaptic depression caused by associative LTD (Salin et al. 1996). If these two forms of plasticity are the only ones operating, and if neither can be reversed, then a point would be reached, due to learning or to random associations, at which the presynaptic terminal is releasing a maximum amount of transmitter and the postsynaptic cell is responding minimally, with no further change possible."

but this is under the assumption that the situation in the ELL is the same as in the cerebellum.

Indeed, see (Han et al. 2000) :

[44] (Han et al. 2000)

"Although both depression and potentiation have been demonstrated experimentally at this synapse (Hirano, 1991), the depression that has been demonstrated has a postsynaptic site of expression (Ito et al., 1982; Sakurai, 1987; Linden et al., 1991; Hemart et al., 1994), whereas the potentiation that has been demonstrated has a presynaptic site of expression (Salin et al., 1996; Linden, 1997) . Thus, the depression and potentiation at the parallel fiber synapse cannot truly reverse each other, and there is a disconnection between the experimental findings regarding synaptic plasticity at this synapse and the reversibility that is necessary for such plasticity to have a role in motor learning."

"Postsynaptic processes are clearly involved in the induction of associative depression since postsynaptic spikes, activation of postsynaptic NMDA receptors, and changes in postsynaptic calcium were all required. But none of these conditions were required for potentiation, and potentiation may therefore be a largely presynaptic phenomenon. The reversibility experiments suggested that the final site of action must be the same for both depression and potentiation, and the paired-pulse facilitation results suggested that this site is located presynaptically. If the final site of expression for depression is indeed presynaptic in the mormyrid ELL, then a retrograde messenger will be necessary for communication between the postsynaptic site of induction and the presynaptic terminal."

"Our results with paired-pulse facilitation suggest a presynaptic site of expression for synaptic depression in ELL, in contrast to the postsynaptic site for the cerebellar LTD that has been examined so far."

A most serious concern however is that na-P cannot profit from the BIE which would make it immune to the ILF-VP, and hence we are left with a system where only the D-component is 'protected' but not the P-component - and that shows when ILF variability is allowed.

Let's have a look at it by 'emulating' the simulation model of Roberts and Bell into demos and let's discuss the emerging problems.

...

The simulation model of Roberts and Bell :

- makes use of a na-P countered by a BSa-D :

[45] (Roberts et al. 2000)

"The in vitro studies presented in [Bell et al., 1997b] show that the learning rule for synaptic change has two components: non-associative enhancement and associative depression. The non-associative enhancement occurs whenever a synapse is active, regardless of the postsynaptic activity."

- models B-spikes as frequency modulated transforms of the B-trigger zone membrane potential amplitude modulation, whenever B-threshold is crossed :

[45] (Roberts et al. 2000)

"In this model of the ELL, a high membrane potential at any time x increases the probability of broad spikes which in turn leads to synaptic depression. On the other hand, a low membrane potential leads to few broad spikes and non-associative plasticity increases the strengths of the corresponding synapses."

- configures PF-input as a timelocked string of presynaptic spike-duets (the A-path ...), each occurring once in a cycle (uniqueness ...), see Fig. 12 :

Fig. 12 from [45] (Roberts et al. 2000)

[45] (Roberts et al. 2000)

"Individual parallel fibers are believed to discharge at specific delays of zero to about 100 msec following each electric organ discharge. The net result is a series of signals at different delays in different parallel fibers. Other types of predictive signals besides the corollary discharge signals, such as proprioceptive and descending electrosensory signals, are probably also involved in adaptive processes [Bastian, 1995, Bell et al., 1997a, Bodznick et al., 1992]."

"There are 300 apical epsps in the simulation (2 at each of the 150 different delays, 1 msec apart) with temporally correlated signals tagged by the arrival time of the signal to the synapse at the apical dendrites."

"The necessary conditions for the ELL to generate a negative image to cancel the fish's own electric organ discharge are: (1) a series of delayed inputs that are correlated with the EOD, and (2) modifiability of parallel fiber synapses in accord with the learning rule. Without the serial delayed inputs, there would be no time-ordered set of inputs from which to sculpt the negative image."

[46] (Williams et al. 2003) (For comparison with Roberts and Bell)

"Each presynaptic cell i spikes exactly once at a fixed time within each sweep of the repeated external input, causing a corresponding postsynaptic potential response (PSP) in the postsynaptic cell."

[47] (Roberts et al. 2010)

"Recordings from the EGp nucleus containing granule cells suggest that the granule cells do not respond to the corollary discharge simultaneously, but their responses appear to be distributed sequentially during the time following the command signal (Bell et al., 1992; Sawtell, 2010) . Following each EOD motor command, different granule cells fire at different latencies so that PF carry a distribution of spikes timed at different delays following each EOD."

- considers presynaptic signals to be a noisy unity :

[45] (Roberts et al. 2000)

"These functions are normalized so that their integrals over one cycle are unity, $\int_0^1 P_n E_i(x_n) dx_n = 1$, and when multiplied by a weighting factor, $w_i(x; t)$, yield the epsp."

- gathers all other input in a noise-factor considered to be purely random :

[45] (Roberts et al. 2000)

"The noise includes epsps that have no consistent temporal relationship with the EOCD signal."

- uses an inner and outer loop structure reminding of the demo program :

[45] (Roberts et al. 2000)

"The representation of time will be broken into cycles parametrized by two variables, $(x; t)$, where x denotes the time following each electric organ command, and t represents the number of EOD cycles."

...

The demo program is to be adapted to deal with the phenomenon of backpropagating spikes (and their threshold). It requires some presentation changes : see Fig. 13.

Fig. 13

Going under the heading 'ELL simulation (MGC)' :

- Signals will be allowed to go negative (inhibiting) - discarding the need to add a constant in S5 - , and hence 'algebraic summation' will replace 'subtraction' in the formulas (it will also cause S4 modulation to be antiphasic to S1).

- S1 to S5 names are kept, but now refer also to the 'content' they are presumed to represent after successful tuning (for decorrelation) : CC, UC, DS, SUM(ApO), iUC

- Apical synapse strengths (and hence ApOs) will be set at a minimal value at the start of a run (instead of S4=S3 as before).

- In this context S4 might become negative, and although mathematically it does not prevent successful decorrelation, it is to be considered as a 'forbidden solution' : hence S4 will not be allowed to go negative, meaning that signal fragments might stop being adjusted, which will show as a worse 'fit'.

- Thresholds will be shown (for the N-spike in blue, for the B-spike in red), with $B > N$ and set at values chosen for display reasons only. A Ca-threshold (with $Ca = B + 20$, see later) will be shown in white.

...

The 'decorrelation formula' itself has to be adapted :

1) A non-associative P has to be introduced :

A na-P can be a % e.g. of the aSS, making SS grow geometrically (exponentially), or a constant, making SS grow arithmetically.

In both cases a 'capping mechanism' may prevent SS from going too high (and anyway saturation would call a stop to it), and in both cases I regard an na-P to be vulnerable to the ILF-VP.

Indeed : while it might be possible to concoct a solution to prevent P to be sensitive to input load variability at a particular synapse, such a solution is impossible when parallel synapses are involved : without a B-spike they cannot 'know' of each other's presence.

I will use a non-capped constant na-P in the next two demos since its arithmetic growth will always be kept in check by a geometrically growing D.

2) The threshold determining the occurrence of a B-spike requires the introduction of Boolean expressions :

The one-line core formula ('enveloped' by the inner and outer loop) now becomes a program snippet of the form :

```
aSS = aSS + constant * ILF                ( na-P )
IF SUM(ApO) + iaDS => threshold(B)
  THEN aSS = aSS - ( SUM(ApO) + iaDS ) * d%  ( BSa-D )
ENDIF
```

After execution the end result is Fig. 13.

See a recording of the execution with <https://www.dropbox.com/s/5pj3785fx5mrfzx/demo-1-27.mp4?dl=0> .

The result is excellent when no ILF variability is allowed, i.e. with ILFMAX=1 (and so is the result in Roberts and Bell's simulation).

See (in the video) how S4 first shows 'a general lift' (effect of na-P) before BSa-D jumps in to 'sculpt' the CC (and note in passing the height S4 has to attain to compensate for the inhibitory iDS).

I added a 'special' yellow line projected over S3 and it represents the sum of apical and basilar output (S3+S4), and hence the membrane potential : it starts married with S3 (when S4=0) , then rises, and only when it crosses B-threshold (the red horizontal) B-spikes occur and BSa-D becomes active, transforming it into the S5=S2 modulation in the end (interrupt the demo regularly to watch it better).

But then see what happens when ILFMAX=2 (and not even 10) : Fig. 14

Fig. 14 <https://www.dropbox.com/s/m10p00w9v947uay/demo-1-28.mp4?dl=0>

The result is terrible.

If - in vivo - ILFMAX can be kept close to 1 (the GrL - as mentioned before - might have some strategies to reduce the variability), then this formula might be acceptable, but I would rather prefer a solution with P 'protected' too.

The obvious line of thinking is to introduce a P that can profit from the BIE and hence must be a BSa-P, but since this P can only start to be active when the signal is above B-threshold, let's keep na-P (but capped now) for when it is below this threshold.

A BSa-P that 'takes over' once B-threshold is crossed, implies that there is another threshold higher up where this P converts to a BSa-D.

This 'Ca-threshold' was already mentioned before when it was noted that the $Next\ SS = aSS - (aSS - aDS) * x\%$ formula permits it ("When all signals are 'lifted into the positive' the sign reversal can be physically correlated with a critical Ca++ level, which on the low side enables P and on the high side enables D.").

The Ca-threshold must be 'set' sufficiently high to allow for 'space' where BSa-P can work, but in fact it is a threshold set in relation to B-spike 'force' and basically independent of the Na-determined membrane potential.

However, since B-spike force itself is a function of how far B-threshold is crossed, we can imagine it as a threshold 'farther up' (in the demos I set it at B-threshold + 20).

...

The 'core formula' will now consist of several parts, one for each type of plasticity, and the effect of all of them is to be added together.

&& SSchange (initialized at 0) will gather the plasticity change components, and will be added to aSS at the end.

SSchange=0

&& na-P with constant step and capped

IF aSS < the capping limit

THEN SSchange = SSchange + (the chosen P-step constant) * ILF

ENDIF

&& BSa-P (force dependent on distance from Ca-threshold !)

IF (SUM(ApO) + iaDS) => B-threshold AND (SUM(ApO) + iaDS) < Ca-threshold

THEN SSchange = SSchange + (Ca-threshold - (SUM(ApO) + iaDS)) * p%

ENDIF

&& BSa-D (force dependent on distance from Ca-threshold !)

IF (SUM(ApO) + iaDS) => B-threshold AND (SUM(ApO) + iaDS) => Ca-threshold

THEN SSchange = SSchange + (Ca-threshold - (SUM(ApO) + iaDS)) * d%

ENDIF

&& SUM(ApO) (concerning S4 and replaced by aSS here) - may not be allowed to go negative.

REPLACE aSS WITH MAX(0 , aSS + SSchange)

If p% and d% would always be the same then the respective formula parts could be merged into one.

...

I thought it to be possible to keep the two Ps from intruding in each other's 'working territory' by capping na-P at B-threshold, but trying it out, it proved that na-P must be allowed to go as high as the B-threshold + the maximum modulatory range [MRMAX] of the DS (as encountered over many iterations), since otherwise a number of modulation minima never get it into B-spike territory, and never get adjusted.

If you wish to see what happens (with BSa-P and BSa-D both = 2% and ILFMAX = 1) :

- with na-P (=1) capped at B-threshold : Fig. 15a <https://www.dropbox.com/s/ygrb5wjuyvu9egw/demo-1-29.mp4?dl=0>
no adaptation at all (the yellow line never crosses the B-threshold).

- with na-P capped at B-threshold + 20 : Fig. 15b <https://www.dropbox.com/s/pf43w4dqj5440vx/demo-1-30.mp4?dl=0>
 adaptation starts up but is restricted to timeslices in the upper half of the modulatory range of S3 (only crests of the yellow line manage to cross the B-threshold).

- with na-P capped at B-threshold + 35 : Fig. 15c <https://www.dropbox.com/s/dnllwcwpkqi67sr/demo-1-31.mp4?dl=0>
 this high and with ILFMAX=1 decorrelation covers the whole range and is excellent although it first has to go through a 'SUM(ApO) building up phase'.

But alas, when ILFMAX=2 : Fig. 15d <https://www.dropbox.com/s/rpaob5fmlpx8ux3/demo-1-32.mp4?dl=0>
 things are spoiled again.

Fig. 15

...

Can we mend matters by having na-P steps much smaller than BSa-D steps ?

Say na-P uses constant steps of only 0.1 :

(taking 5x250 cycles) <https://www.dropbox.com/s/j7fhrmm0ujg2ewp/demo-1-33.mp4?dl=0> .

And with na-P taking steps of just 0.01 ?

(25x250 cycles !) <https://www.dropbox.com/s/bfy99ltuat4vrsf/demo-1-34.mp4?dl=0> .

These demos had ILFMAX=2 (not 10), the final result is indeed very sensitive to the size of the na-P steps (requiring na-P to be very small as a condition to achieve quality) and needing to go through a lot more cycles to achieve it (after going through a phase where things are worse).

[48] (Dean et al. 2010)

"This anti-Hebbian type of relationship can be formalized in the form of spike-time-dependent plasticity, with pronounced LTD occurring for spikes that coincide in a time window of 100-200 ms and much weaker LTP for non-coincident spikes." (My underscore)

Examining the S4 and S5 profiles instead of the fit, it can be seen that the overall fitting is achieved earlier, but a lot of timeslices lag seriously behind in starting to adjust (the vertical cuts in the histograms), affecting - logically - the fit histogram, but affecting also the positioning of the projected 'skylines' (the reciprocal minima are used to 'marry' them).

It might be argued that 'bringing synapses up to working level' is a onetime process and therefore can afford taking some time, but it becomes a speed disadvantage when adaptations are necessary for changes in the CC of the DS.

...

The publication of [50] (Kennedy et al. 2014), mainly focusing on the role of UBCs, nonetheless seems to make also a statement in favour of na-P.

Kennedy et al. based experiments and modelling on the hypothesis that na-P and BSa-D constitute the plasticity rule, referring to studies corroborating this, and yet, several other studies (preceding 2014 by many years) suggest that BSa-P is an active partner in the game.

[42] (Sawtell et al. 2007)

"In contrast to previous in vitro studies, we find that potentiation as well as depression of synaptic responses depends on the timing of B spikes."

[49] (Bell et al. 2008)

"Potentiation as measured in vitro is nonassociative and likely depends on simple repetition of the parallel fiber stimuli at a sufficiently high rate, although in vivo experiments suggest a spike timing-dependent component to the potentiation (Bell et al. 1997b, Sawtell et al. 2007)."

Did I miss the article that cut the knot in this debate ? The demos in this section showed - even with a BSa-P co-engaged - that the use of a na-P component in the presence of ILF-variability weighs heavily on decorrelation quality.

Keeping na-P very small is a way to deal with it, but the cost attached to it is to have to go through many more iterations due to the slow rise towards the B-threshold with many timeslices lagging behind.

...

At some point Kennedy et al. state that in their model (engaging na-P) 1000 EOD cycles seem sufficient to cancel an ESD.

[50] (Kennedy et al. 2014)

"Over the course of about 1000 EOD commands (approximately 5 minutes at EOD command rates typical of paralyzed fish), the membrane potential fluctuation caused by the sensory input is cancelled by the corollary discharge inputs conveyed by granule cells, consistent with the time-course over which negative images are formed in vivo." (My underscore)

I think however that - unintentionally - an 'advantage' (like in a handicap race) was built in, by applying :

[50] (Kennedy et al. 2014)

"The granule cell to medium ganglion cell synapses were strictly positive and their strengths were initially set so that granule cell responses in the absence of EOD driven sensory input generated a roughly flat medium ganglion membrane potential."

This procedure presets (prior to starting the real decorrelation run) the synapse weights to values that already compensate for the ILF variability (keeping $aSS \cdot ILF$ constant). Without this preset and in the presence of ILF variability, decorrelation will need quite more iterations. If I am right then it means that the performance of the model does not match the performance measured in vivo, where having more than just na-P and BSa-D at work remains a real possibility.

...

CONCLUSION

Since the DS must be lifted above B-threshold before BSa-D can come into action, two 'lifting mechanisms' are considered, and since apical synapses must first be potentiated before they can be depressed, na-P seems preferable compared to JLN added excitation.

However, the absence of observations of synaptic density differences between MG1Cs and MG2Cs does not plead in favour of an na-P used to increase ApO, and so does the observation that B-spikes in vivo are sparse, since their action is needed to keep the unrelenting na-P in check.

Sparse B-spiking (in the absence of na-P) allows for good decorrelation as long as - over time - it 'covers' the whole A-path frequently enough.

Most important is that na-P is found lacking because the BIE by definition is not applicable to it, meaning that the variability of the ILF across synapses creates havoc for the decorrelation process, as a demo engaging na-P together with BSa-D shows.

Introducing BSa-P as a third party, and keeping na-P for the initial lift needed to cross B-threshold brings no solace unless na-P is seriously down-sized, as demos show, but that may lead to adaptation slowness in some situations.

With BSa-P participating however, added excitation can be reconsidered.

...

D) SIGNAL 'LIFTING' BY ADDED EXCITATION

Abbreviations used in this section :

ApO	Apical output	JLN	The juxtalobar nucleus
B-spike	Broad spike	MGC	Medium ganglion cell
BIE	The backpropagating integration effect	MG1C	Type 1 MGC
BSa	B-spike associative	MG2C	Type 2 MGC
CC	The correlated component	MR	The modulatory range
D	Depress / Depression	MRMAX	The widest MR encountered over many iterations
DS	The signal to be decorrelated	N-spike	Narrow spike
	iDS The inverted DS	P	Potentiate / Potentiation
ELL	Electrosensory lateral line lobe	na-P	non-associative P
EOCD	Electric organ corollary discharge	PF	Parallel fiber
EOD	Electric organ discharge	SS	Synapse strength
ESD	Electrosensory disturbance	aSS	the actual SS
GrL	Granular layer (or EGP in CB-like structures)	UBC	Unipolar brush cell
ILF	The input load factor	UC	The uncorrelated component
ILF-VP	The ILF variability problem	iUC	The inverted UC
ILFMAX	The maximum value the ILF can take	VP	Variability problem

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

The JLN is known to add an excitatory signal, but it is puzzling to read :

[51] (Mohr et al. 2003b)

"No terminals were observed in the ventrolateral zone where primary afferents from ampullary electroreceptors terminate, suggesting that the juxtalobar nucleus projects exclusively to the mormyromast regions of ELL."

Why not JLN input everywhere ?

Hence, this section might only be relevant for 'the mormyromast region'...

The JLN apparently also engages in converting the spike-latency code from electrosensory afferents into a (burst) rate code for the PriCs, by having it interacting with an EOCD signal (not to be confused with the EOCD coming in via the MFs), but this aspect will not be expanded on here.

...

Let's postulate that BSA-P together with BSA-D now constitute the plasticity rule - with na-P absent or just marginal (in the demos I will now omit it) - and turn again to the option of 'lifting' the iDS at once into B-spike territory by adding an excitatory signal to it.

Note that an excitatory lift alone is of no avail : there must also be a 'P'-component that can strengthen the apical synapses when these are very weak to start with.

In the next two demos I add an excitatory constant of 30 to both S1 and S2 resulting in a 'lift' of 60 for S3 (the basilar output) bringing it 'into the positive' and hence also into 'B-spike territory' : Fig. 16.

(Please take note that in all demos with 'lift' – just for display reasons – S1 and S2 each will take half of the lift of S3), and hence will not appear 'inverted' any more).

See the result with ILFMAX=1 <https://www.dropbox.com/s/vex6lc1nie9kzdz/demo-1-35.mp4?dl=0> : it is excellent !

And with ILFMAX=10 (large ILF variability !) <https://www.dropbox.com/s/nzmmhz3122cqi2xn/demo-1-36.mp4?dl=0> : the result is still very acceptable.

Fig. 16

Have also a look at the height of S4 : it is economical by avoiding heavy synapse density, and ... presuming that MG1Cs and MG2Cs need and receive different 'lifts' it might explain why there are no observations of different synapse density between those two cell types.

...

Importantly, the strategy without na-P also works with sparse B-spiking : the B-spike is necessary for plasticity to occur, but when absent no adaptation deterioration ensues.

A modest 'arithmetic' (constant) non-capped na-P may even remain 'alive' if an occasional B-spike corrects its effect, but it will make S4 go higher, meaning that apical synapses have to grow bigger.

The constant to lift the whole S3 / iDS modulation was deliberately set at 60 here and it ensures that no signal timeslice escapes 'B-spike-treatment'.

It lies in the logic of the proposed scheme that the whole MR of S3 / iDS should lie above B-threshold (but you might already have observed that it does not).

...

It led me to explore the constraints of the lift (its upper and lower limits), and to speculate as to the lift regulation - but let's first note here that 'unwittingly' the P-D balancing problem has been solved :

Up till now, the 'ELL' demos engaging BSA-P and BSA-D had them both set at 2%, and in the 'basic' demos, changing this balance had a profound effect on decorrelation quality.

However, compare in Fig. 17 :

Fig. 17

- a : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/vex6lc1nie9kzdz/demo-1-35.mp4?dl=0>
- b : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/9uejp0bwc9I8a7j/demo-1-48.mp4?dl=0>
- c : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/z9ht76e8k483b2s/demo-1-49.mp4?dl=0>

It appears that the thresholding mechanism holds a bonus : the P and D settings that had to be so carefully balanced may now be set differently, and it has but insignificant consequences.

It is logical : the threshold will determine how often a P or a D 'action' is taken, and if e.g. $p\% \gg d\%$ and one large P-step is taken that overshoots, then several small D-steps will follow to correct it. A larger % will only influence the speed of decorrelation but the balancing is no problem any more : important !

...

Let's now 'seek the limits' by lowering the lift progressively : see Fig. 18.

Fig. 18

Doing this, and arrived at a lift of 52, we see a 'hesitation' in the beginning of the fit histogram (it first goes up but in the end it still delivers excellent decorrelation quality) : Fig. 18a

<https://www.dropbox.com/s/5jtjs1jkffk517q/demo-1-37.mp4?dl=0>

But then, abrupt deterioration appears with just a slightly lower lift (50), and in fact, it is the point where those vertical fissures appear in S4 and S5 : sign of timeslices that get no adjustment at all because the signal snippet they stand for never crosses B-threshold : Fig. 18b <https://www.dropbox.com/s/8b0mymm86cgvfn/demo-1-38.mp4?dl=0>

and it becomes still worse with a lift of 48 : Fig. 18c <https://www.dropbox.com/s/hi0um8i5orjtset/demo-1-39.mp4?dl=0> (all demos here with ILFMAX=1 : NO ILF variability).

The surprising observation in the first 'hesitating' demo here is that the MR of S3 can plunge quite deep UNDER the B-threshold while decorrelation is still excellent over all 250 timeslices, see Fig. 19a. (at the red dots)

Fig. 19

However, when we seek the lower limit while omitting S2 (keeping only the iCC or S1), the MR of S3 (hence = S1) can be seen to stay just above B-threshold : see Fig. 19b <https://www.dropbox.com/s/ecoff5jjm28p5hu/demo-1-40.mp4?dl=0> .

The lift used here (Fig. 20a) was 41 and with just one less (40) the 'fissures' appear (Fig. 20b)

<https://www.dropbox.com/s/bfhxgdrvrepbm0h/demo-1-41.mp4?dl=0> .

Fig. 20

Here the rule can indeed be said to be that the whole iCC-signal (its MR) should be lifted above B-threshold.

But while S1 (the iCC) at timeslice level is a constant, S2 (the iUC) is not.

The consequence of the addition of the random S2 / iUC is that it allows for a limit lower than B-threshold by an amount equal to the difference between maximum and minimum of S2, taken over all (and enough) iterations (MRMAX of S2).

The randomness of S2 at each iteration 'offers a chance' to each timeslice signal snippet to cross the B-threshold, but a boost of the size of the MRMAX is the best it can offer.

...

In vivo though, the UC is so weak compared to the CC, that I presume its effect to be insignificant.

The ILF for a particular synapse may help to boost the related timeslice signal snippet to cross B-threshold, but it is not random in relation to the synapse itself.

Even 'ambient noise' may be an important player, but we will shortly identify another strong and random factor, and so the 'actual lower limit' may have its own 'lowest limit' depending on the combination of random factors at work.

There is also an upper limit for the lift to respect : see what happens : Fig. 21

for a lift of 62 : Fig. 21a <https://www.dropbox.com/s/bt8vf47f9xob089/demo-1-42.mp4?dl=0>

for a lift of 66 : Fig. 21b <https://www.dropbox.com/s/kcksv0t89af032h/demo-1-43.mp4?dl=0>

for a lift of 70 : Fig. 21c <https://www.dropbox.com/s/86eknys3ouddg8u/demo-1-44.mp4?dl=0> .

Fig. 21

The cause here is that S4 (the SUM(ApO)) 'is touching bottom' (it is forbidden to go negative) and with its lowest parts being amputated it starts to have insufficient amplitude, losing 'depressing power'.

I try again - by omitting S2 - to get more insight : Fig. 22.

Compare Fig. 22a : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/ztcj6pyyevv4h5x/demo-1-45.mp4?dl=0> (with lift of 43)

with Fig. 22b : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/u4fu7xhrg6ib619w/demo-1-46.mp4?dl=0> (with a lift of just four more : 47).

Fig. 22

The apexes of S3 (= S1 here) touch the Ca-threshold, and when they start transgressing decorrelation quality begins to suffer.

However, if the Ca-threshold is not transgressed (see S3), when then is BSa-D in action ?

It is not ! When BSa-D is turned off in the demo we get an identical result : compare Fig. 22a with Fig. 22c

<https://www.dropbox.com/s/xhoj1c5z6fpt423/demo-1-47.mp4?dl=0> .

When S4 / SUM(ApO) starts from nothing, B-spikes are not powerful enough to reach the Ca-threshold but DO sculpt the apical synapses as a function of iDS modulation, building a SUM(ApO) profile that is an antiphase signal of the iDS (being = iCC here).

The fact that NO B-spike means NO P and a 'minimal' B-spike (it will always have some strength) provokes a forceful P, creates kind of a sharp transition zone : and it is this phenomenon that makes that once an apical synapse gets the chance of being activated while a B-spike occurs, it gets an amount of P that ensures that it can keep participating in the decorrelation process.

One could call this 'a bootstrap P' and remember the 'fissures' in the histograms : if S4 is allowed to start with a high enough value (and not from 0) then these fissures don't appear anymore (I suspect that - in vivo - P and D cannot take great 'leaps', and in that case multiple B-spike 'lucky strikes' are necessary).

With the apical component SUM(ApO) growing and added to the lifted iDS, B-spikes get stronger, but loose P-power when approaching the Ca-threshold, doing nothing when they get there, but by that time decorrelation is done.

When experiments start with synapses 'at working strength' it may well be that BSa-D is the prominent plastic change to be observed when an artificial UC is added to the DS, the BSa-P (and not na-P) taking over when the signal is withdrawn and the system 'recovers'.

It can be speculated about if the Ca-threshold represents a sharp demarcation line between P and D, or if it is a 'region' in which opposing P and D 'forces' annul each other.

...

When adding an S2 / iUC signal, the lift must be adjusted upwards to compensate for the (also inverted) average S2 signal strength (reason why the lift is lower in Fig. 20 than in Fig. 18 and lower in Fig. 22 than in Fig. 21), and being random, there is no question any more of 'apexes' not violating the Ca-threshold, but we will see a signal dancing up and down of it, and I presume that the integral of these ups and downs will approach zero after many iterations.

As a consequence, BSa-D and BSa-P have to 'dance' too, always a step too late for total decorrelation (and hence a somewhat lesser final fit), but without the BSa-D partner decorrelation would freeze, unable to adapt for the overshoots and settling for an average of the undershoots in the iUC.

Again, the UC in vivo being so small compared to the CC, the rule that the DS MRMAX must stay below the Ca-threshold might hold, but other and stronger random signals merging with it cause the limit to become 'fuzzy' here too.

...

Taking it together with the earlier limit rule : the 'strict' rule is that the DS MRMAX should be positioned between the B- and the Ca-threshold (and better not be squeezed between the two), but in practice random signals allow for trespassing these limits by an amount that is a function of their own MRMAX.

Hence, the added lift together with the B-threshold are candidates to be adjustable to guarantee that these limit rules are not too much violated, the 'lift' being the input delivered by the JLN, and the B-threshold being under the control of the preeminent nucleus.

The JLN-signal might be viewed as potentially corrupting the DS. However, insofar it is correlated with the EOD, it will in principle be decorrelated out. It is to be understood that the decorrelation process only applies to the signal parts that transgress the B-spike threshold, and hence the 'lift'-portion beneath it is in any case preserved.

...

CONCLUSION

'Lifting' the DS and engaging BSa-P and BSa-D gives excellent decorrelation, doesn't need constant B-spiking, and - when well adjusted - can be economical regarding apical synapse density, but there are limits to respect, which are explored.

On the low side lurks the risk that particular timeslices never relate to a signal strong enough to cross the B-threshold, with the corresponding synapses never engaging in plastic change.

On the high side lurks the risk that particular timeslices always relate to a signal so strong that the corresponding synapses cannot be depressed any more.

Random factors however allow sharp limiting borders to extend into 'fuzzy' transition zones with a probability factor that dwindles going outward until an absolute outer limit is met.

Once the lower outer limit is crossed from the outside, powerful P attracts the synapse across the transition zone by having it generating its own excitatory lift, and P alone is even sufficient to realize decorrelation, but D is necessary to prevent 'freezing' and to allow for downward SS corrections when subsequent environmental changes or overshoots due to random fluctuations occur.

It is the function of the JLN imported excitation to push all timeslices of the complete signal at least into this lower transition zone.

It begs the question if JLN added excitation is self-regulating, and if the preeminent nucleus might also play an adjusting role, by translating the limits themselves.

...

J) THE 'TRAFFIC DENSITY FLUCTUATION SIGNAL'

Abbreviations used in this section :

AP	Action potential	LGC	Large ganglion cell
AS	The activating signal	MGC	Medium ganglion cell
ApO	Apical output	MG1C	Type 1 MGC
B-spike	Broad spike	MR	The modulatory range
BIE	The backpropagating integration effect	na	non-associative
CC	The correlated component	N-spike	Narrow spike
D	Depress / Depression	P	Potentiate / Potentiation
DS	The signal to be decorrelated	PF	Parallel fiber
EffC	Efferent cell	PriC	Principal cell
ELL	Electrosensory lateral line lobe	PuC	Purkinje(-like) cell
EOCD	Electric organ corollary discharge	SS	Synapse strength
GS	Guiding signal	aSS	Actual SS
ILF	The input load factor	TDFS	The traffic density fluctuation signal
ILFMAX	The maximum value the ILF can take	UC	The uncorrelated component
JLN	The juxtalobar nucleus	UWA	Uncorrelated wrong addressing
LFuC	Large fusiform cell		

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

Recall the UWA problem : PF-PuC synapses activated by PF 'traffic' totally unrelated to the 'local' DS. It is not to be considered 'white noise', it can appear suddenly, and can stay away for a while.

These synapses also engage in an 'averaging process' when their activation coincides with a B-spike, but since their activation is not correlated with the DS they end up making an average of a load of randomly picked timeslices of the DS.

Their SSs then reflect some 'global' average of the DS, and when these synapses are activated, they all together represent 'added excitation' coming in by the apical dendrites.

Fig. 23

The JLN probably can adapt to compensate for the excitation component which – on average – is always present (the 'common load', being the part under the MR, see Fig. 23).

The unpredictable (since DS-uncorrelated) fluctuations in it however represent an UC-signal coming in via the apical dendrites that will be added to the UC which comes in by the basilar dendrites, hence corrupting the desired UC output. The apical UC constitutes for the PriCs an UC which is indistinguishable from the basilar UC they are supposed to extract, and therefore this signal is to be annulled at all costs.

I will call this DS-uncorrelated 'intruding' signal, which will be reflecting the 'traffic density' on the PFs, the 'Traffic density fluctuation signal' [TDFS].

We should be aware that there might be a lot of very fluctuating 'passing-through traffic' in the PFs crossing a PuC dendritic tree, and consider that it is not without impact.

I'm not sure if simulations in publications do take this background effect into account.

To see how the ELL might tackle the problem we need to take another look at its neurocircuitry.

...

Let's zoom out of MGCs to look at the larger picture.

The ELL comes with up to 6 PriC types, each cell type pairing with a partner type handling inverted basilar input, see Fig. 24.

Fig. 24 from [52] (Mohr et al. 2003a)

They display characteristics that seem to predestinate them all for a decorrelating function : basilar input from electroreceptors, apical input via the PFs from a granular layer.

All these cells then should be expected to be able to backpropagate an AP into their apical dendrites, but only the MGC pair features an additional B-spike of which backpropagating is clearly demonstrated, apparently relieving its N-spikes to do the same.

The efferent cells [EffCs] are the large fusiform cells [LFuCs] and its partner type the large ganglion cells [LGCs] : they are less numerous than MGCs, and also less lush in dendritic arborization.

[53] (Sawtell et al. 2007)

"In comparison to efferent cells, MGcells are more numerous, have more apical dendrites, and have dendrites with a greater density of spines (Meek et al., 1996) . Thus, the majority of parallel fiber synaptic contacts are onto MG cells, and these cells must have a central role in adaptive processing in ELL . However, MGcells affect the output of ELL only indirectly, via their inhibition of ELL efferent cells."

[52] (Mohr et al. 2003a)

"MG cells, however, are four times as numerous as efferent cells, have twice as many apical dendrites, and have twice as many spines per unit length of apical dendrite (Meek et al. 1996) . Parallel fiber synapses on MG cells are therefore +16 times more numerous than parallel fiber synapses on efferent cells."

I cannot find persuasive confirmation for their N-spike being able to backpropagate,

[54] (Grant et al. 1998)

"Our hypothesis is that these waves are caused by dendritic spikes that are initiated in the somas or the proximal apical dendrites of medium ganglion cells, large ganglion cells, and large fusiform cells and propagated into the distal apical dendrites."

"Propagation of dendritic action potentials in the apical dendrites of large ganglion and large fusiform could explain this earlier wave."
(Note : I believe MGCs do, but LFCs and LGCs ?)

and there is even doubt of 'serious' (compared to MGCs) plasticity occurring in their apical dendritic trees.

[55] (Roberts et al. 2000)

"MG cells show greater synaptic plasticity than the similarly situated efferent cells (Bell, unpublished observation)."

...

The LFCs (and LGCs) come into focus if we are prepared to make a bold assumption : they might function as TDFS sensors, and to do that they have no need for backpropagating spikes for plasticity sculpting at their apical synapses (if N-spikes could backpropagate, why 'invent' a B-spike ?).

If plasticity is necessary at these synapses, it is only to bring them up to a 'standard working strength' on active PF-lines, (the synapses involved with DS-uncorrelated activity in the MGCs also converge to a value leading to an individual signal output – aSS*ILF - that is the same across them) and in EffCs a capped na-P could serve the purpose without a backpropagating spike to be associated with (if not capped some spike associated D is necessary).

I suppose that it is not necessary to have an ample apical dendritic tree as MGCs have, to be able to get a 'good enough' measure of the TDFS.

The SUM(ApO) of the LFC - an excitatory cell - will then 'carry' a TDFS (due to variability in amount of active PFs) which is comparable to the TDFS of the DS-uncorrelated activity 'sensed' by MG1Cs, and when it is merged with the output of the MG1C - this cell being inhibitory - the mutual signals (one inverted, antiphase) will annul each other (if properly calibrated), 'purifying' the output of the EffC of this 'polluting' factor.

The TDFS of the LFuC includes the total traffic, while the TDFS of the MGC only represents the uncorrelated traffic (the correlated TDFS component being compensated for by the BIE), but I presume the 'correlated traffic' to be much less dense than the uncorrelated one.

...

The LFuCs and the LGCs might need 'lift' just as the MGCs, and maybe therefore also get basilar input and JLN input, but to what extent is lift necessary in relation to an N-threshold ? If the presumed role of these cells is to generate a TDFS 'measured' by their apical dendrites, then the basilar DS (UC + CC !) and the JLN EOOD are unwanted signals, corrupting their purpose.

The basilar signal (the modulations - not the pure lift it provides) should in some way be 'flattened' in these cell types : reading [56] (Bell et al. 1997) I'm not sure if it is in favour of the proposed idea, but it looks to me as if the basilar input MR is being 'smothered' here.

[56] (Bell et al. 1997)

"Corollary discharge responses of large ganglion cells : the corollary discharge had variable effects in cells of this type. The most common response (11/27 cells) was a complex of low amplitude "ripples" in which the excitatory and inhibitory effects of the corollary discharge appeared to be almost balanced so that the response was essentially flat at the resting membrane potential."

"The corollary discharge responses of most large ganglion and large fusiform cells were quite small and largely inhibitory in the absence of previous pairing with an electrosensory stimulus, in comparison with the strong excitatory responses of interneurons such as the medium ganglion cell, the morphologically unidentified II cells, or granule cells."

"In several efferent cells, the absence of a strong corollary discharge response at the resting membrane potential was shown to be attributable to a balance between excitatory and inhibitory synaptic inputs to the cell. Thus, the strong excitatory corollary discharge responses in the initial stages of processing are not present at the output stage."

...

With the proposed 'modus operandi' scheme in the cytoarchitectural setup of the mormyromast region in the mormyrid ELL in mind, it is interesting to compare it with the cytoarchitecture of the ELL of gymnotiform fish as examined by Bastian et al. .

Pyramidal cells here show graded morphology and plasticity with at one end of the continuum cells that have lush dendritic arborisation, and are capable of decorrelation by plastic change, and at the other end cells with sparser arborisation and showing no plasticity.

[57] (Bastian et al. 2004)

"Pyramidal cells show marked variation in their morphology, including dendritic structure, which is correlated with physiological diversity."

"A subset of cells, those with the largest apical dendrites, are plastic, but those with the smallest dendrites are not."

"We hypothesize that Ca²⁺ entry via NMDA receptors plus Ca²⁺ and NR2B associated signaling cascades are critical constituents of the molecular machinery underlying pyramidal cell adaptive plasticity; further, we propose that lack of the NR2B subunit and Ca²⁺ signaling proteins accounts for the nonplastic nature of the small-dendrite cells. Additional in vitro studies involving direct manipulation of these intracellular signaling systems are needed to verify this hypothesis."

The distinct properties of these 'end of the spectrum cells' seem to reflect the alleged property differences for MGCs and EffCs in the mormyrids.

...

CONCLUSION

The LFuCs are proposed to be TDFS sensors (and not decorrelating devices).

With 'uniform synapse strength' in the apical dendrites (if a backpropagating AP should nonetheless be demonstrated, it might be useful to create 'synaptic democracy') the SUM(ApO) would generate a TDFS (representing the time course of the ILF-variability mostly due to the non-correlated PF-traffic).

When this signal is merged with the inverted input from the inhibiting MGCs - which also picked up the TDFS with their UWA-synapses (which converge to equality too since uncorrelated) - then the TDFS in the EffC output is erased : an 'antiphase annulling technique'.

This function is compatible with LFuCs being less numerous, having less dendritic arborization, and having no backpropagating spikes (or using them 'for democracy only').

While basilar dendrites of LFuCs may be useful to receive input for lifting reasons, any modulated input there should now be discarded since it would corrupt the TDFS which the LFuCs are supposed to generate.

Several studies seem to argue for LFuC basilar MR being 'flattened' (maybe also by 'antiphase annulling').

The ELL in gymnotiform fish might also display TDFS sensing cells in the form of non-plastic pyramidal cells.

...

GENERAL CONCLUSION

Abbreviations used in this section :

AS	The activating signal	GrC	Granule cell
ASS	Activating signal strength	GrL	Granular layer (or EGp in CB-like structures)
B-spike	Broad spike	GS	Guiding signal
BIE	The backpropagating integration effect	MGC	Medium ganglion cell
CC	The correlated component	MR	The modulatory range
DS	The signal to be decorrelated	PF	Parallel fiber
EffC	Efferent cell	PriC	Principal cell
EGp	Eminentia granularis posterior	PuC	Purkinje(-like) cell
ELL	Electrosensory lateral line lobe	SS	Synapse strength
EOCD	Electric organ corollary discharge	TDFS	The traffic density fluctuation signal
FFI	Feedforward inhibition	UBC	Unipolar brush cell
GoC	Golgi cell	UC	The uncorrelated component

With the GrL of the cerebellum in mind, it is striking to find a GrL in the EGp of the ELL in which GrCs seem to be exclusively devoted to the sequenced activation of PF-MGC synapse populations : they are not involved in the processing of the electrosensory input itself (the DS) which comes in by the basilar MGC dendrites. Obviously, it raises the question to what extent the state of affairs is different in the cerebellum.

The signals which the EGp-GrCs receive by MFs are baptized 'guiding signals' (GSs), they are derived from corollary discharge, secondary UBC activation or internal 'body-state' parameters, and they determine the activation sequence by the use of combinatorial input to AND-gating GrCs.

To obtain decorrelation, the memory activating sequence should evolve 'aligned in time' with the DS so that each DS timeslice can be bound to an exclusive MGC synapse set. This way the MGC can 'compute' averages of each DS timeslice as the DS repetitively occurs. It involves a method (like the use of B-spiking) to integrate the DS in an appropriate plasticity mechanism at the synapses.

The averaging finally results in the storing of a CC image which is the inverse of the CC in the received DS which makes the MGC produce an output signal that represents the UC in this electrosensory DS.

The characteristics, the interrelationships and the combinatorial capacities of the GSs were explored, and a lot of 'caveats' were formulated : memory addressing needs to be reliably reproducible, and the average related memory content at each address is to be safeguarded against corruption by the compounding of different timeslice DS values (the 'uniqueness' requirement). All this is also potentially relevant for the cerebellum.

It would indeed be devastating for decorrelation if a process that generates 'timing diversity' triggers the same GrCs more than once during the sequence devolution in synchrony with the DS.

The 'synchrony' itself is questioned if it depends on a trigger signal (the EOCD) and ensuing cascaded UBC activity (time-locked) – it is more guaranteed when it can depend on internal reference signals (state-locked), even when UBCs are co-engaged for resolution requirements.

GoCs in the GrL may play an important role in minimizing repeated GrC firing by imposing a high level of inhibition (enforcing strict AND-gating) and by brisk FFI to cut the firing short.

The MGC soma membrane potential, result of (algebraically) summed apical and basilar (DS) output, is transformed into B-spike force and/or burst frequency. Backpropagating into the apical dendrites it delivers the info that is to direct the plasticity process. 'Excitatory lift' must be added to the DS (done by way of the JLN EOCD input) to raise the membrane potential into the range (the limits of which are explored) where the total MR of the DS can be of influence on the B-spike.

It is stressed that SSs and presynaptic ASSs co-determine MGC apical output, and that consequently SSs should compensate for ASS differences across GrCs. The summation process at the soma automatically takes care of it, and with the B-spike 'uploading' the result it is called the 'backpropagating integration effect' – the BIE. Differences in activated PF volumes across timeslices are also compensated this way. A BIE can only be effective though when a bidirectional B-spike associated plasticity rule is in vigour, as demos show.

An MGC output corrupting signal is identified that cannot be dealt with by the BIE : it is caused by the presynaptic activations by 'passing-through' traffic in the PF population which is uncorrelated with the DS. It is proposed that this

'traffic density fluctuating signal' (TDFS) is apically 'picked up' by the EffCs (assuming that without a B-spike mechanism they are not dedicated to decorrelation, and that their basilar DS input is 'neutralized'), and that the EffCs annul the antiphase TDFS component in the MGC output by merging their outputs.

Of course, it raises the question how the cerebellum itself might tackle the ILF-VP and TDFS phenomena

...

I hope that the foregoing considerations incite to approach the cerebellum from a somewhat different angle of view. Does it implement decorrelation as does the ELL, or does it apply 'a variation on the theme' ? What to expect from PuCs that have no basilar dendrites ? What to expect from a seemingly homogeneous GrC population that sends up AFs that bifurcate into PFs which cross the PuC dendritic trees ? Cerebellar GrCs have more dendrites than those in the EGp of the ELL : it must be challenging for AND-gating and it also poses connectivity issues ...

All this (and more) is discussed in Part 2 (the cerebellum) which consists of the following sections :

- | | |
|--|---|
| A) AND-gating | G) Patch and PF types |
| B) Digitalization | H) From MGC to PuC |
| C) Connectivity | I) MLIs |
| D) Modality control | J) The basic algorithm ? |
| E) Input space issues | K) The cerebello-cerebral conversation |
| F) DS and GSs on the scale of the cerebellum | Addendum : 'Random connectivity examined' |

...

ADDENDUM to 'MEMORY ADDRESSING IN CEREBELLO – TIME-LOCKED'

UBCs always have just ONE input.

A cascade starts with ONE MF triggering ONE UBC, and when such an UBC triggers secondary UBCs (all with just ONE input) all these secondary UBCs are downstream of just the original MF and no other.

Such cascades do not interweave (no excitatory interconnections) and hence I say they are 'diverging only' (Raymond seems to contradict this, but I think that her ref of Dino does not support the statement of reciprocal connectivity : the restriction to one input in a cascading system precludes it).

[58] (Raymond et al. 2018)

"There are reciprocal connections between groups of excitatory unipolar brush cells (UBCs) (Dino et al. 2000), between groups of inhibitory GoCs (Hull & Regehr 2012), and between groups of inhibitory molecular layer interneurons (MLIs) (Rieubland et al. 2014)."

When an UBC connects to a GrC the 'diverging' stops since a GrC is an 'end-station' : its output no more triggers still other UBCs but goes directly to the PuCs.

GrCs however have multiple inputs and hence - at this level only - convergence of the outputs of different UBC cascades is possible : when such GrC inputs are AND-gated it will tend to sparsen and to shorten the GrC-output (UBCs can output long firing sequences).

...

Only by intercalation of Golgi cells [GoCs] can a cascade have inhibiting effects upon other cascades, but when the original input of the involved cascades is the same, GoCs also will react always the same.

By doing so they will change the firing characteristics of a field of UBC cascades (maybe also helping to cut short the long firing of UBCs), but they do not necessarily introduce a 'chaotic factor' (a factor that leads to the production of ever-changing outputs whenever the same input is given : it would be detrimental for the requirement of 'reproducibility').

Reproducibility is no problem in silico (everything in a computer is designed to guarantee reproducibility of output), but it is a hazard in vivo - hence my concern that UBC cascades might fail in their final output being reproducible enough.

Conversely, it is a 'hazard' for (bottom-up) simulations NOT to 'inject' enough randomness by way of random functions (which must be reseeded (*) to be really random !), since otherwise the reproducibility in the simulation is totally artificial. (*) Moreover, the 'seeding' is clock dependent, meaning that some time must elapse before a next seed value will be different from the former one : an important concern when reseeding occurs in an ultrafast loop.

...

Quite some simulations assume that GoCs and not UBCs are the generators of timing diversity.

[59] (Kennedy et al. 2014)

"Whereas most models of cerebellar granular layer function, posit pivotal roles for Golgi cell inhibition of granule cells in expansion recoding, our study suggests a key role for UBCs."

[60] (Medina et al. 2000)

"The ability of simulated granule cells to fire at different times during the CS arises naturally as a consequence of the complex patterns of granule cell excitation and inhibition that result from dynamic interactions among mossy fibers, granule cells and Golgi cells."

Never I see that the problem of reproducibility in the face of randomness is discussed.

I prefer UBCs to GoCs because the number of entry points is equal to the number of involved cascades and hence much more restricted ('the smaller size of the EOCD carrying MF bundle') - reducing the randomness hazard (while GoC-only based systems have to deal with a large MF-population for input).

There are other reasons to prefer UBCs to GoCs : GoCs have already an impressive load of other functions to implement, and see also :

[61] (Johansson et al. 2016)

"Another possibility, suggested by a number of computational models, is that inhibitory inputs from Golgi cells could be used to sculpt temporal patterns in granule cells. Recently, it has been shown that the main time constant over which the spontaneous firing of Golgi cells has an effect in vivo is on the order of seconds. This time constant could allow Golgi cell activity to set excitability levels and increase the fidelity of quite some granule cell responses on long time scales. However, this scale is probably too long for generating temporal patterns in the 10–100 millisecond range."

...

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Addendum ‘Memory addressing in cerebello – time-locked’

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